
The algebraic and geometric classification of derived Jordan and bicommutative algebras *

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Abstract: *We developed a new proper method for classifying n -dimensional derived Jordan algebras, and apply it to the classification of 3-dimensional derived Jordan algebras. As a byproduct, we have the algebraic classification of 3-dimensional metabelian commutative algebras and 3-dimensional derived commutative associative algebras. After that, we introduced a method of classifying n -dimensional bicommutative algebras, based on the classification of n -dimensional derived commutative associative algebras, and applied it to the classification of 3-dimensional bicommutative algebras. The second part of the paper is dedicated to the geometric classification of 3-dimensional metabelian commutative, derived commutative associative, derived Jordan and bicommutative algebras.*

Keywords: *Jordan algebras, bicommutative algebras, metabelian algebras, algebraic classification, geometric classification.*

MSC2020: 17A30 (primary); 17D25, 14L30 (secondary).

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*The authors would like to thank the SRMC (Sino-Russian Mathematics Center in Peking University, Beijing, China) for its hospitality and excellent working conditions, where some parts of this work have been done. The work is supported by FCT 2023.08031.CEECIND and UID/00212/2025.

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Introduction

The algebraic classification (up to isomorphism) of algebras of dimension n of a certain variety defined by a family of polynomial identities is a classic problem in the theory of non-associative algebras, see [1–4, 6, 30, 35, 38–40]. There are many results related to the algebraic classification of small-dimensional algebras in different varieties of associative and non-associative algebras. For example, algebraic classifications of 2-dimensional algebras, 3-dimensional Poisson algebras, 4-dimensional alternative algebras, 5-dimensional symmetric Leibniz algebras and so on have been given. Deformations and geometric properties of a variety of algebras defined by a family of polynomial identities have been an object of study since the 1970s, see [5, 6, 9, 10, 17, 28, 29, 31] and references in [35, 37, 43].

Jordan algebras are the most popular type of non-associative algebras[¶]. The first Jordan algebras appeared in a classical paper by Jordan, von Neumann, and Wigner in 1934 [33], and until now they have been under active investigation. The most famous generalizations of Jordan algebras are the following: non-commutative Jordan algebras (see, [1] and references therein); terminal algebras (see, [38] and references therein); commutative $\mathcal{C}\mathcal{D}$ -algebras (see, [34] and references therein); axial algebras (see, [13] and references therein); structurable algebras (see, [20] and references therein); and so on. In the present paper, we introduce another generalization of Jordan algebras. Namely, we are studying commutative derived Jordan algebras. The idea of considering derived algebras arose from the study of the lower central series in groups. Namely, for a variety of algebras defined by a family of polynomial identities Ω , we say that an algebra A is a derived Ω -algebra if A^2 is an Ω -algebra. One of the basic examples of derived Ω -algebras is metabelian (also known as 2-step solvable) algebras, i.e., algebras satisfying the identity $(xy)(zt) = 0$. They are in the intersection of all non-(anti)commutative derived Ω -algebras. Metabelian algebras from a certain variety of algebras are of a certain interest now [14, 18, 41, 44, 45, 47, 48]. The notion of derived algebras plays an important role in many varieties of algebras. So, each derived algebra of a solvable Lie or Leibniz algebra will be nilpotent; each derived algebra of a bicommutative (or anti-bicommutative) algebra (under the Jordan product) is commutative associative [12, 27]. Hence, our results are given in subsection 1.2 (classification of derived commutative associative algebras) play an important role in the future classification of 3-dimensional bicommutative algebras, given in subsection 1.4.

The systematic study of bicommutative algebras from the algebraic point of view started after a paper by Dzhumadil'daev and Tulenbaev [27], where they proved that bicommutative algebras are Lie admissible and derived commutative associative under the Jordan product. The main results from the theory of bicommutative algebras were obtained by Dzhumadil'daev and Drensky with various co-authors. Namely, Dzhumadil'daev, Ismailov, and Tulenbaev constructed bases for free bicommutative algebras and proved that the bicommutative operad is not Koszul [26]. Dzhumadil'daev and Ismailov described all identities of commutator and anticommutator algebras of bicommutative algebras [25]. Drensky found the bases of polynomial identities of 2-dimensional non-associative bicommutative algebras and showed that one of these algebras generates the whole variety of bicommutative algebras [21]. Later, he found analogies of classical re-

[¶]Due to many connections between associative and Lie algebras, we consider both as staying outside of the "non-associative world".

sults of the invariant theory of finite groups acting on polynomial algebras, namely analogies of the Endlichkeitssatz of Emmy Noether, the Molien formula, and the Chevalley-Shephard-Todd theorem. Finally, he describes the symmetric polynomials of free bicommutative algebras [22]. Invariants of free metabelian bicommutative algebras were also studied in a paper by Ögüslü and Fındık [46]. Drensky and Zhakhayev obtained a positive solution to the Specht problem for bicommutative algebras [24]. Finally, Drensky, Ismailov, Mustafa, and Zhakhayev established various superanalogs of classical theorems for bicommutative superalgebras in [23]. Ismailov, Mashurov, and Sartayev proved that every metabelian Lie algebra can be embedded into a bicommutative algebra with respect to the commutator product [32]. Products of commutator ideals of bicommutative algebras were studied in a paper by Kaygorodov, Mashurov, Nam, and Zhang [36]. Bai, Chen, and Zhang proved that the Gelfand-Kirillov dimension of a finitely generated bicommutative algebra is a nonnegative integer [7]. Shestakov and Zhang gave an example of wild automorphisms of the free two-generated bicommutative algebra in [49]. Bialgebra theory for bicommutative algebras was established in [8]. Towers introduced the Frattini theory for bicommutative algebras [50]. Kolesnikov and Sartayev proved that the Hadamard product of the bicommutative operad with the Novikov operad coincides with their white Manin product [42]. The bicommutative operad also satisfies the Dong property [19]. Bicommutative algebras are one of the most important subvarieties in Lie-admissible algebras (about Lie-admissible algebras see [18]). Bicommutative algebras are algebras of biderivation-type [11]. Burde and Dekimpe described bicommutative algebraic structures on certain Lie algebras in [15, 16]. Some results regarding algebraic and geometric classifications of small-dimensional nilpotent bicommutative algebras were obtained by Abdurasulov, Kaygorodov, Khudoyberdiyev, Páez-Guillán, and Voronin [4, 39, 40]. We also mention that bicommutative algebras are a particular case of δ -Novikov algebras for $\delta = 0$, and the present paper will finish the classification of 3-dimensional δ -Novikov algebras (for the case of $\delta \notin \{0, 1\}$ see [3]).

The present paper aims to give the complete algebraic and geometric classification of 3-dimensional algebras in the following varieties: metabelian commutative, derived commutative associative, derived Jordan, and bicommutative algebras. Namely, subsection 1.1 is dedicated to the algebraic classification of 3-dimensional metabelian commutative algebras, which is presented in Theorem A1; subsection 1.2 is dedicated to the algebraic classification of 3-dimensional derived commutative associative algebras, which is presented in Theorem A2; subsection 1.3 is dedicated to the algebraic classification of 3-dimensional derived Jordan algebras, which is presented in Theorem A3. The next subsection 1.4 contains the algebraic classification of 3-dimensional bicommutative algebras (Theorem A4). Based on the obtained results, we present the geometric classifications:

Theorem G1 states that the variety of 3-dimensional metabelian commutative algebras is 8-dimensional with 2 irreducible components and with 1 rigid algebra.

Theorem G2 states that the variety of 3-dimensional derived commutative associative algebras is 12-dimensional with 2 irreducible components and with 1 rigid algebra.

Theorem G3 states that the variety of 3-dimensional derived Jordan algebras is 12-dimensional with 7 irreducible components and with 5 rigid algebras.

Theorem G4 states that the variety of 3-dimensional bicommutative algebras is 10-dimensional with 4 irreducible components and with 1 rigid algebra.

1 The algebraic classification of algebras

All the algebras below will be over \mathbb{C} and all the linear maps will be \mathbb{C} -linear. For simplicity, every time we write the multiplication table of an algebra, the products of basic elements whose values are zero or can be recovered from the commutativity or from the anticommutativity are omitted. The notion of a nontrivial algebra means that the multiplication is nonzero.

The following propositions are well known and, for example, the multiplication tables of algebras can be found in [1].

Proposition 1 (see [1]). *Let \mathfrak{J} be a nontrivial complex 2-dimensional Jordan algebra. Then \mathfrak{J} is isomorphic to one of the following algebras:*

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{J}_{01} & : e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_2e_2 = e_2 \\ \mathfrak{J}_{02} & : e_1e_1 = e_1 \\ \mathfrak{J}_{03} & : e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_1e_2 = e_2 \\ \mathfrak{J}_{04} & : e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_1e_2 = \frac{1}{2}e_2 \\ \mathfrak{J}_{05} & : e_1e_1 = e_2 \end{aligned}$$

All algebras, excepting \mathfrak{J}_{04} , are associative.

Proposition 2 (see [1]). *Let J be a complex 3-dimensional commutative associative algebra. Then J is isomorphic to one of the following algebras:*

$$\begin{aligned} J_{01} & : e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_2e_2 = e_2 \\ J_{02} & : e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_1e_2 = e_2 \\ J_{03} & : e_1e_1 = e_1 \\ J_{04} & : e_1e_1 = e_2 \\ J_{05} & : e_1e_2 = e_3 \\ J_{06} & : e_1e_1 = e_2 & e_1e_2 = e_3 \\ J_{07} & : e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_2e_2 = e_2 & e_3e_3 = e_3 \\ J_{08} & : e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_2e_2 = e_2 & e_2e_3 = e_3 \\ J_{09} & : e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_1e_2 = e_2 & e_1e_3 = e_3 \\ J_{10} & : e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_1e_2 = e_2 & e_1e_3 = e_3 & e_2e_2 = e_3 \\ J_{11} & : e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_2e_2 = e_3 \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 3 (see [1]). *Let J be a complex 3-dimensional Jordan algebra. Then J is a commutative associative algebra listed in Proposition 2 or isomorphic to one of the following algebras:*

$$\begin{aligned} J_{12} & : e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_2e_2 = e_2 & e_3e_3 = e_1 + e_2 & e_1e_3 = \frac{1}{2}e_3 & e_2e_3 = \frac{1}{2}e_3 \\ J_{13} & : e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_1e_2 = \frac{1}{2}e_2 & e_1e_3 = e_3 \\ J_{14} & : e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_1e_2 = \frac{1}{2}e_2 & e_1e_3 = \frac{1}{2}e_3 \\ J_{15} & : e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_2e_2 = e_3 & e_1e_2 = \frac{1}{2}e_2 \\ J_{16} & : e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_2e_2 = e_3 & e_1e_2 = \frac{1}{2}e_2 & e_1e_3 = e_3 \\ J_{17} & : e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_2e_2 = e_2 & e_1e_3 = \frac{1}{2}e_3 & e_2e_3 = \frac{1}{2}e_3 \\ J_{18} & : e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_1e_2 = \frac{1}{2}e_2 \\ J_{19} & : e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_2e_2 = e_2 & e_1e_3 = \frac{1}{2}e_3 \end{aligned}$$

1.1 Metabelian commutative algebras

Definition 4. An algebra A is called a metabelian algebra if it satisfies $(xy)(zt) = 0$.

Theorem A1. Let A be a complex 3-dimensional metabelian commutative algebra. Then A is isomorphic to one of the following algebras:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
M_{01} & : e_1e_1 = e_2 \\
M_{02} & : e_1e_2 = e_3 \\
M_{03} & : e_1e_1 = e_2 \quad e_1e_2 = e_3 \\
M_{04}^\alpha & : e_1e_3 = e_1 \quad e_2e_3 = \alpha e_2 \\
M_{05} & : e_1e_3 = e_1 \quad e_3e_3 = e_2 \\
M_{06} & : e_1e_3 = e_1 + e_2 \quad e_2e_3 = e_2 \\
M_{07} & : e_1e_3 = e_1 \quad e_2e_2 = e_1
\end{array}$$

All algebras, excepting $M_{04}^\alpha \cong M_{04}^{\alpha^{-1}}$, are non-isomorphic. Algebras M_{01} , M_{02} , and M_{03} are associative.

Proof. It is easy to see that we have only two opportunities: $\dim A^2 = 2$ and $\dim A^2 = 1$.

First, we consider algebras with $\dim A^2 = 2$. The multiplication table of A is defined as follows:

$$A : e_1e_3 = C_{131}e_1 + C_{132}e_2 \quad e_2e_3 = C_{231}e_1 + C_{232}e_2 \quad e_3e_3 = C_{331}e_1 + C_{332}e_2$$

If $(C_{131}, C_{232}) = (0, 0)$ and $C_{132}C_{231} = 0$, then A is an associative algebra, giving rise to the algebra M_{03} .

We now turn to the case where $(C_{131}, C_{232}) \neq (0, 0)$ or $C_{132}C_{231} \neq 0$. Since $\dim A^2 = 2$, the matrix

$$\mathfrak{C} = \begin{pmatrix} C_{131} & C_{132} \\ C_{231} & C_{232} \\ C_{331} & C_{332} \end{pmatrix}$$

necessarily has rank 2. For convenience, we encode the multiplication by the triple $\theta = (B_1, B_2, B_3)$, where

$$\begin{array}{l}
B_1 = C_{131}\nabla_{13} + C_{231}\nabla_{23} + C_{331}\nabla_{33}, \\
B_2 = C_{132}\nabla_{13} + C_{232}\nabla_{23} + C_{332}\nabla_{33}, \\
B_3 = 0.
\end{array}$$

Here ∇_{ij} denotes the symmetric bilinear form satisfying

$$\nabla_{ij}(e_p, e_q) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } (p, q) = (i, j) \text{ or } (p, q) = (j, i), \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Then the product in A is given by

$$x \cdot y = \theta(x, y) = B_1(x, y)e_1 + B_2(x, y)e_2, \quad x, y \in A.$$

Both B_1 and B_2 are nonzero because $\dim A^2 = 2$.

The group $GL_3(\mathbb{C})$ acts on algebra structures via a change of the basis. For $\phi \in GL_3(\mathbb{C})$, the transformed structure is

$$\theta * \phi = (B'_1, B'_2, B'_3), \quad (\theta * \phi)(x, y) := \phi^{-1}(\theta(\phi(x), \phi(y))), \quad x, y \in A.$$

By construction, $\phi: (A, \theta) \rightarrow (A, \theta * \phi)$ is an algebra isomorphism, so $(A, \theta) \cong (A, \theta * \phi)$. Conversely, any isomorphism between such algebras arises from a change of basis; thus, classifying these algebras up to isomorphism amounts to describing the orbits of this action.

To simplify the structure constants, we may choose a transformation of the form

$$\phi = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & 0 & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ 0 & 0 & a_{33} \end{pmatrix}, \quad a_{11}a_{22}a_{33} \neq 0.$$

Then the transformed component B'_1 becomes

$$B'_1 = \frac{a_{33}(C_{131}a_{11} + C_{231}a_{21})}{a_{11}} \nabla_{13} + \frac{C_{231}a_{22}a_{33}}{a_{11}} \nabla_{23} + \frac{a_{33}(2C_{131}a_{13} + 2C_{231}a_{23} + C_{331}a_{33})}{a_{11}} \nabla_{33}.$$

From here, we may assume $B_1 \in \{\nabla_{13}, \nabla_{23}, \nabla_{33}\}$, i.e.,

$$(C_{131}, C_{231}, C_{331}) \in \{(1, 0, 0), (0, 1, 0), (0, 0, 1)\}.$$

- $(C_{131}, C_{231}, C_{331}) = (1, 0, 0)$.
 - If $C_{232} \notin \{0, 1\}$, we choose ϕ to be the following matrix:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{C_{132}}{1-C_{232}} & 1 & -\frac{C_{332}}{2C_{232}} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $\theta * \phi = (\nabla_{13}, C_{232}\nabla_{23}, 0)$. So we get the algebras $M_{04}^{\alpha \notin \{0, 1\}}$. Furthermore, $M_{04}^\alpha \cong M_{04}^\beta$ if $\alpha = \beta^{-1}$.

- If $C_{232} = 0$, then $C_{332} \neq 0$ since the matrix \mathfrak{C} has rank 2. Choose ϕ as follows:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{132} & C_{332} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $\theta * \phi = (\nabla_{13}, \nabla_{33}, 0)$. Thus we obtain the algebra M_{05} .

- If $C_{232} = 1$ and $C_{132} = 0$, we choose ϕ to be the following matrix:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -\frac{1}{2}C_{332} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $\theta * \phi = (\nabla_{13}, \nabla_{23}, 0)$. So we get the algebra M_{04}^1 .

- If $C_{232} = 1$ and $C_{132} \neq 0$, we choose ϕ to be the following matrix:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & C_{132} & -\frac{1}{2}C_{332} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $\theta * \phi = (\nabla_{13}, \nabla_{13} + \nabla_{23}, 0)$. Therefore we get the algebra M_{06} .

- $(C_{131}, C_{231}, C_{331}) = (0, 1, 0)$. Then $C_{232} \neq 0$ or $C_{132}C_{231} \neq 0$.

- If $C_{132} \neq 0$, we choose ϕ' to be the following matrix:

$$\begin{pmatrix} C_{132}^{-\frac{1}{2}} & 0 & -\frac{1}{2}C_{332}C_{132}^{-\frac{3}{2}} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C_{132}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $\theta * \phi' = (\nabla_{23}, \nabla_{13} + \alpha \nabla_{23}, 0)$ where $\alpha = C_{132}^{-\frac{1}{2}}C_{232}$. Consider the following matrices and let $\phi'' = \varphi_1$ if $\alpha^2 + 4 = 0$ and $\phi'' = \varphi_2$ if $\alpha^2 + 4 \neq 0$:

$$\varphi_1 = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{2}{\alpha} & \frac{2}{\alpha} & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{2}{\alpha} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \varphi_2 = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{\alpha^2 + 4} - \alpha) & -\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{\alpha^2 + 4} + \alpha) & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{\alpha^2 + 4} - \alpha) \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then

$$\theta * \phi' \phi'' \in \{(\nabla_{13}, \nabla_{13} + \nabla_{23}, 0), (\nabla_{13}, \beta \nabla_{23}, 0)\}.$$

Hence, there are no new algebras.

- If $C_{132} = 0$, then $C_{232}C_{332} \neq 0$. Let ϕ be the following matrix:

$$\phi = \begin{pmatrix} C_{332}C_{232}^{-3} & -C_{332}C_{232}^{-3} & 0 \\ C_{332}C_{232}^{-2} & 0 & -\frac{1}{2}C_{332}C_{232}^{-2} \\ 0 & 0 & C_{232}^{-1} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $\theta * \phi = (\nabla_{13}, \nabla_{33}, 0)$. So we get the algebra M_{05} .

- If $(C_{131}, C_{231}, C_{331}) = (0, 0, 1)$, then $C_{232} \neq 0$. Consider the following matrix:

$$\phi = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & C_{232}^{-2} & 0 \\ 1 & -C_{132}C_{232}^{-3} & -\frac{1}{2}(C_{132} + C_{232}C_{332})C_{232}^{-3} \\ 0 & 0 & C_{232}^{-1} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $\theta * \phi = (\nabla_{13}, \nabla_{33}, 0)$. Therefore, there are no new algebras.

Second, we consider algebras with $\dim A^2 = 1$. Then let $\{e_1, e_2, e_3\}$ be a basis of A such that $A^2 = \langle e_1 \rangle$. Then the nontrivial multiplications in A is given as follows:

$$A : e_1e_2 = C_{121}e_1 \quad e_1e_3 = C_{131}e_1 \quad e_2e_2 = C_{221}e_1 \quad e_2e_3 = C_{231}e_1 \quad e_3e_3 = C_{331}e_1$$

If $(C_{121}, C_{131}) = (0, 0)$, then A is associative, yielding the algebras M_{01} and M_{02} .

We now consider the case $(C_{121}, C_{131}) \neq (0, 0)$. Define $\theta: A \times A \rightarrow A$ by

$$\theta = C_{221}\nabla_{22} + C_{331}\nabla_{33} + C_{121}\nabla_{12} + C_{131}\nabla_{13} + C_{231}\nabla_{23}.$$

Let $\phi \in GL_3(\mathbb{C})$ and write $\theta * \phi = \theta'$. Then $(A, \theta) \cong (A, \theta')$. Now, we choose $\phi = \phi_1$ where

$$\phi_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ 0 & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $\theta' = C'_{221}\nabla_{22} + C'_{331}\nabla_{33} + C'_{121}\nabla_{12} + C'_{131}\nabla_{13} + C'_{231}\nabla_{23}$, where

$$\begin{aligned} C'_{121} &= C_{121}a_{22} + C_{131}a_{32}, \\ C'_{131} &= C_{121}a_{23} + C_{131}a_{33}. \end{aligned}$$

Since $(C_{121}, C_{131}) \neq (0, 0)$, we may assume $(C'_{121}, C'_{131}) = (0, 1)$. Next, we choose $\phi = \phi_2$ if $C'_{221} = 0$ or $\phi = \phi_3$ if $C'_{221} \neq 0$ where

$$\phi_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -C'_{231} & -\frac{1}{2}C'_{331} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \phi_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -C'_{231}(C'_{221})^{-\frac{1}{2}} & -\frac{1}{2}C'_{331} \\ 0 & (C'_{221})^{-\frac{1}{2}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $\theta' * \phi \in \{\nabla_{13}, \nabla_{13} + \nabla_{22}\}$. Then we get the algebras M_{04}^0 and M_{07} . □

1.2 Derived commutative associative algebras

Definition 5. A commutative algebra A is called a derived commutative associative algebra if the derived algebra A^2 is a commutative associative algebra.

It is clear that any metabelian commutative algebra is a derived commutative associative algebra. The variety of derived commutative associative algebras contains all commutative associative algebras. Let A be a derived commutative associative algebra. If either $A^2 = A$ or $A^2 = 0$, then A is a commutative associative algebra.

Theorem A2. Let A be a complex 3-dimensional derived commutative associative algebra. Then A is a metabelian commutative algebra listed in Theorem A1, or a commutative associative algebra listed in Proposition 2, or it is isomorphic to one of the following algebras:

$$\begin{aligned} A_{01}^{\alpha, \beta, \gamma} &: e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_2e_2 = e_2 & e_1e_3 = \alpha e_2 \\ & & e_2e_3 = \beta e_1 & e_3e_3 = e_1 + \gamma e_2 \\ A_{02}^\alpha &: e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_2e_2 = e_2 & e_1e_3 = e_2 & e_2e_3 = \alpha e_1 \\ A_{03}^\alpha &: e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_2e_3 = e_2 & e_3e_3 = \alpha e_1 \\ A_{04}^\alpha &: e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_2e_3 = e_1 + e_2 & e_3e_3 = \alpha e_1 \\ A_{05}^{\alpha, \beta} &: e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_1e_3 = e_2 & e_2e_3 = \alpha e_1 + e_2 & e_3e_3 = \beta e_1 \\ A_{06}^\alpha &: e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_1e_3 = e_2 & e_2e_3 = e_1 & e_3e_3 = \alpha e_2 \\ A_{07} &: e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_1e_3 = e_2 \\ A_{08} &: e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_1e_3 = e_2 & e_3e_3 = e_2 \\ A_{09}^\alpha &: e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_1e_3 = e_2 & e_3e_3 = e_1 + \alpha e_2 \\ A_{10} &: e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_2e_3 = e_1 & e_3e_3 = e_2 \\ A_{11} &: e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_3e_3 = e_1 + e_2 \\ A_{12}^{\alpha, \beta} &: e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_1e_2 = e_2 & e_1e_3 = e_1 \\ & & e_2e_3 = \alpha e_1 & e_3e_3 = \beta e_1 + e_2 \\ A_{13}^\alpha &: e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_1e_2 = e_2 & e_1e_3 = e_1 \\ & & e_2e_3 = e_1 & e_3e_3 = \alpha e_1 \\ A_{14}^\alpha &: e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_1e_2 = e_2 & e_1e_3 = e_1 & e_3e_3 = \alpha e_1 \\ A_{15}^\alpha &: e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_1e_2 = e_2 & e_2e_3 = e_1 & e_3e_3 = e_1 + \alpha e_2 \\ A_{16} &: e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_1e_2 = e_2 & e_3e_3 = e_1 + e_2 \\ A_{17} &: e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_1e_2 = e_2 & e_3e_3 = e_1 \end{aligned}$$

A_{18}	:	$e_1e_1 = e_1$	$e_1e_2 = e_2$	$e_2e_3 = e_1$	$e_3e_3 = e_2$
A_{19}	:	$e_1e_1 = e_1$	$e_1e_2 = e_2$	$e_2e_3 = e_1$	
A_{20}	:	$e_1e_1 = e_1$	$e_1e_2 = e_2$	$e_3e_3 = e_2$	
A_{21}^α	:	$e_1e_1 = e_2$	$e_2e_3 = e_1 + e_2$	$e_3e_3 = \alpha e_2$	
A_{22}	:	$e_1e_1 = e_2$	$e_2e_3 = e_1$		
A_{23}	:	$e_1e_1 = e_2$	$e_2e_3 = e_1$	$e_3e_3 = e_2$	
A_{24}^α	:	$e_1e_1 = e_2$	$e_1e_3 = e_1$	$e_2e_3 = \alpha e_2$	
A_{25}	:	$e_1e_1 = e_2$	$e_1e_3 = e_1$	$e_3e_3 = e_2$	
A_{26}	:	$e_1e_1 = e_2$	$e_1e_3 = e_1 + e_2$	$e_2e_3 = e_2$	
A_{27}	:	$e_1e_1 = e_2$	$e_3e_3 = e_1$		
A_{28}	:	$e_1e_1 = e_2$	$e_2e_3 = e_2$	$e_3e_3 = e_1$	
A_{29}	:	$e_1e_1 = e_1$	$e_2e_3 = e_1$		
A_{30}	:	$e_1e_1 = e_1$	$e_3e_3 = e_1$		

All listed algebras are non-isomorphic, excepting:

$$A_{01}^{\alpha,\beta,\gamma} \cong A_{01}^{-\alpha,\beta,\gamma} \cong A_{01}^{\alpha,-\beta,\gamma} \cong A_{01}^{\beta\gamma^{-\frac{1}{2}},\alpha\gamma^{-\frac{1}{2}},\gamma^{-1}}, \quad A_{02}^\alpha \cong A_{02}^{\alpha^{-1}}, \quad A_{06}^\alpha \cong A_{06}^{-\alpha}, \quad A_{09}^\alpha \cong A_{09}^{-\alpha}, \quad A_{15}^\alpha \cong A_{15}^{-\alpha}.$$

Proof. **Firstly**, we consider the case when $\dim A^2 = 2$. We may assume

$$A^2 = \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \in \{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_{01}, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_{02}, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_{03}, \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_{05}\},$$

where $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_{04}$ is excluded, as it is non-associative. Extend a basis $\{e_1, e_2\}$ of A^2 to a basis $\{e_1, e_2, e_3\}$ of A . Since our aim is to classify non-associative algebras A , we only consider those cases where the multiplication on A is not associative. The associative algebras among these possibilities have already been described in Proposition 2. Hence, in what follows, we assume that A is non-associative.

I. $A^2 = \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_{01}$. Then the multiplication table of A is defined as follows:

$$A : \begin{array}{lll} e_1e_1 = e_1 & e_1e_3 = C_{131}e_1 + C_{132}e_2 & e_2e_3 = C_{231}e_1 + C_{232}e_2 \\ & e_2e_2 = e_2 & e_3e_3 = C_{331}e_1 + C_{332}e_2 \end{array}$$

Without loss of generality, we may assume $C_{131} = C_{232} = 0$ via the change of basis:

$$e'_1 = e_1, \quad e'_2 = e_2, \quad e'_3 = -C_{131}e_1 - C_{232}e_2 + e_3.$$

Further if $C_{131} = C_{232} = 0$, then A is a commutative associative algebra precisely when

$$C_{331} = C_{332} = C_{132} = C_{231} = 0.$$

Hence we assume $(C_{331}, C_{332}, C_{132}, C_{231}) \neq (0, 0, 0, 0)$. Now, let us consider the following cases:

- If $C_{331} \neq 0$, then with the change of basis: $e'_1 = e_1$, $e'_2 = e_2$, $e'_3 = C_{331}^{-\frac{1}{2}}e_3$, we get the family of algebras $A_{01}^{\alpha,\beta,\gamma}$. Moreover,

$$A_{01}^{\alpha,\beta,\gamma} \cong A_{01}^{\alpha',\beta',\gamma'} \text{ if } \alpha^2 = \alpha'^2, \beta^2 = \beta'^2, \gamma = \gamma' \text{ or } \alpha^2 = \gamma\beta'^2, \beta^2 = \gamma\alpha'^2, \gamma\gamma' = 1.$$

- If $C_{331} = 0$ and $C_{332} \neq 0$, then with the change of basis:

$$e'_1 = e_2, \quad e'_2 = e_1, \quad e'_3 = C_{332}^{-\frac{1}{2}} e_3,$$

we get the family of algebras $A_{01}^{\alpha, \beta, 0}$.

- If $C_{331} = C_{332} = 0$ and $C_{132} \neq 0$, then after changing

$$e'_1 = e_1, \quad e'_2 = e_2, \quad e'_3 = C_{132}^{-1} e_3,$$

we get the family of algebras A_{02}^α . Furthermore, $A_{02}^\alpha \cong A_{02}^\beta$ if $\alpha = \beta^{-1}$.

- If $C_{331} = C_{332} = C_{132} = 0$, then after changing $e'_1 = e_2, e'_2 = e_1, e'_3 = C_{231}^{-1} e_3$, we get the algebra A_{02}^0 .

II. $A^2 = \tilde{J}_{02}$. The nontrivial multiplications in A is given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} A : \quad e_1 e_1 &= e_1 & e_1 e_3 &= C_{131} e_1 + C_{132} e_2 & e_2 e_3 &= C_{231} e_1 + C_{232} e_2 \\ & & & & e_3 e_3 &= C_{331} e_1 + C_{332} e_2 \end{aligned}$$

Applying the change of basis: $e'_1 = e_1, e'_2 = e_2, e'_3 = -C_{131} e_1 + e_3$, we may assume $C_{131} = 0$. In this reduced form, the algebra A is commutative and associative precisely when

$$C_{331} = C_{132} = C_{231} = C_{232} = 0.$$

Since $\dim A^2 = 2$, it follows that $(C_{232}, C_{132}, C_{332}) \neq (0, 0, 0)$.

- If $C_{232} \neq 0$, then, with the change of basis:

$$e'_1 = e_1, \quad e'_2 = e_2, \quad e'_3 = -\frac{C_{332}}{2C_{232}^2} e_2 + \frac{1}{C_{232}} e_3,$$

we can make $C_{232} = 1$ and $C_{332} = 0$. So we assume $C_{232} = 1$ and $C_{332} = 0$.

- If $C_{132} = C_{231} = 0$, we get the family of algebras A_{03}^α .
- If $C_{132} = 0$ and $C_{231} \neq 0$, then after changing $e'_1 = e_1, e'_2 = C_{231}^{-1} e_2, e'_3 = e_3$, we get the family of algebras A_{04}^α .
- If $C_{132} \neq 0$, then with the change of basis: $e'_1 = e_1, e'_2 = C_{132} e_2, e'_3 = e_3$, we get the family of algebras $A_{05}^{\alpha, \beta}$.
- If $C_{232} = 0$ and $C_{132} \neq 0$, then with the change of basis: $e'_1 = e_1, e'_2 = C_{132} e_2, e'_3 = e_3$, we can make $C_{132} = 1$. So we assume $C_{132} = 1$.

- If $C_{231} \neq 0$, then with the change of basis:

$$e'_1 = e_1, \quad e'_2 = C_{231}^{-\frac{1}{2}} e_2, \quad e'_3 = -\frac{1}{2} C_{331} C_{231}^{-\frac{3}{2}} e_2 + C_{231}^{-\frac{1}{2}} e_3,$$

we get the family of algebras A_{06}^α . Moreover, $A_{06}^\alpha \cong A_{06}^\beta$ if and only if $\alpha = -\beta$.

- If $C_{231} = C_{331} = C_{332} = 0$, we get the algebra A_{07} .
- If $C_{231} = C_{331} = 0$ and $C_{332} \neq 0$, then by changing

$$e'_1 = e_1, \quad e'_2 = C_{332}^{-1} e_2, \quad e'_3 = C_{332}^{-1} e_3,$$

we get the algebra A_{08} .

- If $C_{231} = 0$ and $C_{331} \neq 0$, then by changing

$$e'_1 = e_1, \quad e'_2 = C_{331}^{-\frac{1}{2}} e_2, \quad e'_3 = C_{331}^{-\frac{1}{2}} e_3,$$

we get the family of algebras A_{09}^α . Moreover, $A_{09}^\alpha \cong A_{09}^\beta$ if and only if $\alpha = -\beta$.

- If $C_{232} = C_{132} = 0$, then $C_{332} \neq 0$ since $\dim A^2 = 2$. Moreover, we have $(C_{231}, C_{331}) \neq (0, 0)$ since otherwise A is a commutative associative algebra. Then with the change of basis: $e'_1 = e_1$, $e'_2 = e_2$, $e'_3 = C_{332}^{-\frac{1}{2}} e_3$ we can make $C_{332} = 1$. So we assume $C_{332} = 1$.

- If $C_{231} \neq 0$, then with the change of basis:

$$e'_1 = e_1, \quad e'_2 = C_{231}^{-\frac{2}{3}} e_2, \quad e'_3 = -\frac{1}{2} C_{231}^{-\frac{4}{3}} C_{331} e_2 + C_{231}^{-\frac{1}{3}} e_3,$$

we get the algebra A_{10} .

- If $C_{231} = 0$, then $C_{331} \neq 0$ and with the change of basis:

$$e'_1 = e_1, \quad e'_2 = C_{331}^{-1} e_2, \quad e'_3 = C_{331}^{-\frac{1}{2}} e_3,$$

we get the algebra A_{11} .

III. $A^2 = \tilde{J}_{03}$. Then the nontrivial multiplications in A is given as follows:

$$\begin{array}{llll} A : & e_1 e_1 = e_1 & e_1 e_3 = C_{131} e_1 + C_{132} e_2 & e_2 e_3 = C_{231} e_1 + C_{232} e_2 \\ & & e_1 e_2 = e_2 & e_3 e_3 = C_{331} e_1 + C_{332} e_2 \end{array}$$

Then with the change of basis: $e'_1 = e_1$, $e'_2 = e_2$, $e'_3 = -C_{232} e_1 - C_{132} e_2 + e_3$, we can make $C_{132} = C_{232} = 0$. So we assume $C_{132} = C_{232} = 0$. Hence the nontrivial multiplications in A is given as follows:

$$A : \quad e_1 e_1 = e_1 \quad e_1 e_2 = e_2 \quad e_1 e_3 = C_{131} e_1 \quad e_2 e_3 = C_{231} e_1 \quad e_3 e_3 = C_{331} e_1 + C_{332} e_2$$

So A is a commutative associative algebra if $C_{131} = C_{231} = C_{331} = C_{332} = 0$.

- We consider the case $C_{131} \neq 0$.
 - If $C_{332} \neq 0$, then by changing $e'_1 = e_1$, $e'_2 = C_{332} C_{131}^{-2} e_2$, $e'_3 = C_{131}^{-1} e_3$, we get the family of algebras $A_{12}^{\alpha, \beta}$.
 - If $C_{332} = 0$ and $C_{231} \neq 0$, then by changing
$$e'_1 = e_1, \quad e'_2 = C_{131} C_{231}^{-1} e_2, \quad e'_3 = C_{131}^{-1} e_3,$$
we get the family of algebras A_{13}^{α} .
 - If $C_{332} = C_{231} = 0$, then by changing $e'_1 = e_1$, $e'_2 = e_2$, $e'_3 = C_{131}^{-1} e_3$, we get the family of algebras A_{14}^{α} .
- Now, we consider the second case when $C_{131} = 0$ and $C_{331} \neq 0$.
 - If $C_{231} \neq 0$, then by changing $e'_1 = e_1$, $e'_2 = C_{331}^{\frac{1}{2}} C_{231}^{-1} e_2$, $e'_3 = C_{331}^{-\frac{1}{2}} e_3$, we get the family of algebras A_{15}^{α} . Moreover, $A_{15}^{\alpha} \cong A_{15}^{\beta}$ if and only if $\alpha = -\beta$.
 - If $C_{231} = 0$ and $C_{332} \neq 0$, then by changing
$$e'_1 = e_1, \quad e'_2 = C_{332} C_{331}^{-1} e_2, \quad e'_3 = C_{331}^{-\frac{1}{2}} e_3,$$
we get the algebra A_{16} .
 - If $C_{231} = C_{332} = 0$, then by changing $e'_1 = e_1$, $e'_2 = e_2$, $e'_3 = C_{331}^{-\frac{1}{2}} e_3$, we get the algebra A_{17} .
- Finally, we consider the third case when $C_{131} = 0$ and $C_{331} = 0$.
 - If $C_{231} C_{332} \neq 0$, then with the change of basis:

$$e'_1 = e_1, e'_2 = C_{332}^{\frac{1}{3}} C_{231}^{-\frac{2}{3}} e_2, e'_3 = C_{231}^{-\frac{1}{3}} C_{332}^{-\frac{1}{3}} e_3,$$

we get the algebra A_{18} .

- If $C_{231} \neq 0$ and $C_{332} = 0$, then with the change of basis:

$$e'_1 = e_1, e'_2 = e_2, e'_3 = C_{231}^{-1} e_3,$$

we get the algebra A_{19} .

- If $C_{231} = 0$, then since A is non-associative, we have $C_{332} \neq 0$. Then, with the change of basis: $e'_1 = e_1, e'_2 = C_{332} e_2, e'_3 = e_3$, we get the algebra A_{20} .

IV. $A^2 = \tilde{J}_{05}$. Then the nontrivial multiplications in A is given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} A : \quad e_1 e_1 &= e_2 & e_1 e_3 &= C_{131} e_1 + C_{132} e_2 & e_2 e_3 &= C_{231} e_1 + C_{232} e_2 \\ & & & & e_3 e_3 &= C_{331} e_1 + C_{332} e_2 \end{aligned}$$

Then with the change of basis: $e'_1 = e_1, e'_2 = e_2, e'_3 = -C_{132} e_1 + e_3$, we can make $C_{132} = 0$. So we assume $C_{132} = 0$. Moreover, A is associative if

$$C_{131} = C_{231} = C_{331} = C_{232} = 0.$$

Since $\dim A^2 = 2$, we have $(C_{131}, C_{231}, C_{331}) \neq (0, 0, 0)$.

- Case $C_{231} \neq 0$. If we consider the change of basis:

$$e'_1 = e_1 - \frac{C_{131}}{C_{231}} e_2, e'_2 = e_2, e'_3 = \frac{C_{131} C_{232}}{C_{231}^2} e_1 - \frac{2C_{232} C_{131}^2 + C_{231} C_{331}}{2C_{231}^3} e_2 + \frac{1}{C_{231}} e_3,$$

we can make $C_{231} = 1$ and $C_{131} = C_{331} = C_{132} = 0$. Whence, the nontrivial multiplications in A is given as follows:

$$A : \quad e_1 e_1 = e_2 \quad e_2 e_3 = e_1 + C_{232} e_2 \quad e_3 e_3 = C_{332} e_2$$

- If $C_{232} \neq 0$, then by changing $e'_1 = C_{232} e_1, e'_2 = C_{232}^2 e_2, e'_3 = C_{232}^{-1} e_3$, we get the family of algebras A_{21}^α .
- If $C_{232} = C_{332} = 0$, then we get the algebra A_{22} .
- If $C_{232} = 0$ and $C_{332} \neq 0$, then with the change of basis:

$$e'_1 = C_{332}^{\frac{1}{4}} e_1, e'_2 = C_{332}^{\frac{1}{2}} e_2, e'_3 = C_{332}^{-\frac{1}{4}} e_3,$$

we get the algebra A_{23} .

- Case $C_{231} = 0$ and $C_{131} \neq 0$. Then, with the change of basis:

$$e'_1 = e_1, e'_2 = e_2, e'_3 = -\frac{1}{2} C_{331} C_{131}^{-2} e_1 + C_{131}^{-1} e_3,$$

we may assume $C_{131} = 1$ and $C_{331} = 0$. Whence, the nontrivial multiplications in A is given as follows:

$$A : \quad e_1 e_1 = e_2 \quad e_1 e_3 = e_1 + C_{132} e_2 \quad e_2 e_3 = C_{232} e_2 \quad e_3 e_3 = C_{332} e_2$$

- If $C_{232} \notin \{0, 1\}$, then with the change of basis:

$$e'_1 = e_1 - \frac{C_{132}}{C_{232}-1} e_2, e'_2 = e_2, e'_3 = -\frac{1}{2} C_{332} C_{232}^{-1} e_2 + e_3,$$

we get the algebras $A_{24}^{\alpha \notin \{0,1\}}$. Moreover, $A_{24}^\alpha \cong A_{24}^\beta$ if and only if $\alpha = \beta$.

- If $C_{232} = C_{332} = 0$, then with the change of basis:

$$e'_1 = e_1 + C_{132}e_2, e'_2 = e_2, e'_3 = e_3,$$

we get the algebra A_{24}^0 .

- If $C_{232} = 0$ and $C_{332} \neq 0$, then by changing

$$e'_1 = C_{332}^{\frac{1}{2}}e_1 + C_{132}C_{332}^{\frac{1}{2}}e_2, e'_2 = C_{332}e_2, e'_3 = e_3,$$

we get the algebra A_{25} .

- If $C_{232} = 1$ and $C_{132} = 0$, then with the change of basis:

$$e'_1 = e_1, e'_2 = e_2, e'_3 = -\frac{1}{2}C_{332}e_2 + e_3,$$

we get the algebra A_{24}^1 .

- If $C_{232} = 1$ and $C_{132} \neq 0$, then with the change of basis:

$$e'_1 = C_{132}e_1, e'_2 = C_{132}^2e_2, e'_3 = -\frac{1}{2}C_{332}e_2 + e_3,$$

we get the algebra A_{26} .

- If $C_{231} = C_{131} = 0$, then $C_{331} \neq 0$ and we consider the following subcases.

- If $C_{232} = 0$, then with the change of basis:

$$e'_1 = C_{331}e_1 + C_{332}e_2, e'_2 = C_{331}^2e_2, e'_3 = e_3,$$

we get the algebra A_{27} .

- If $C_{232} \neq 0$, then with the change of basis:

$$e'_1 = C_{331}C_{232}^{-2}e_1, e'_2 = C_{331}^2C_{232}^{-4}e_2, e'_3 = -\frac{1}{2}C_{332}C_{232}^{-2}e_2 + C_{232}^{-1}e_3,$$

we get the algebra A_{28} .

Secondly, we consider the case when $\dim A^2 = 1$ and $A^2A^2 \neq 0$ (i.e., A is not metabelian). We may assume $A^2 = \langle e_1 \rangle$ such that $e_1e_1 = e_1$. Extend a basis $\{e_1\}$ of A^2 to a basis $\{e_1, e_2, e_3\}$ of A . Then the nontrivial multiplications in A is given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} A : \quad e_1e_1 &= e_1 & e_2e_2 &= C_{221}e_1 & e_3e_3 &= C_{331}e_1 \\ e_1e_2 &= C_{121}e_1 & e_1e_3 &= C_{131}e_1 & e_2e_3 &= C_{231}e_1 \end{aligned}$$

Then A is associative if the following relations hold:

$$C_{221} = C_{121}^2, \quad C_{331} = C_{131}^2, \quad C_{121}C_{131} = C_{231}.$$

Define $\theta: A \times A \rightarrow A$ by

$$\theta = \nabla_{11} + C_{221}\nabla_{22} + C_{331}\nabla_{33} + C_{121}\nabla_{12} + C_{131}\nabla_{13} + C_{231}\nabla_{23}.$$

Let $\phi \in GL_3(\mathbb{C})$ and write $\theta * \phi = \theta'$. Then $(A, \theta) \cong (A, \theta')$. Now, we choose $\phi = \phi_1$ where:

$$\phi_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -C_{121} & -C_{131} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix},$$

then $\theta' = \nabla_{11} + C'_{221}\nabla_{22} + C'_{331}\nabla_{33} + C'_{231}\nabla_{23}$, where

$$C'_{221} = C_{221} - C_{121}^2, \quad C'_{331} = C_{331} - C_{131}^2, \quad C'_{231} = C_{231} - C_{121}C_{131}.$$

Since A is non-associative, $(C'_{221}, C'_{331}, C'_{231}) \neq (0, 0, 0)$. Next we choose $\phi = \phi_2$ where:

$$\phi_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ 0 & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $\theta' * \phi = \nabla_{11} + C''_{221} \nabla_{22} + C''_{331} \nabla_{33} + C''_{231} \nabla_{23}$, where

$$\begin{aligned} C''_{221} &= C'_{221} a_{22}^2 + 2C'_{231} a_{22} a_{32} + C'_{331} a_{32}^2, \\ C''_{331} &= C'_{221} a_{23}^2 + 2C'_{231} a_{23} a_{33} + C'_{331} a_{33}^2, \\ C''_{231} &= C'_{221} a_{22} a_{23} + C'_{231} a_{22} a_{33} + C'_{231} a_{23} a_{32} + C'_{331} a_{32} a_{33}. \end{aligned}$$

Whence,

$$\begin{pmatrix} C''_{231} & C''_{331} \\ -C''_{221} & -C''_{231} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{33} & -a_{23} \\ -a_{32} & a_{22} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} C'_{231} & C'_{331} \\ -C'_{221} & -C'_{231} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{32} & a_{33} \end{pmatrix}.$$

So, we may assume $(C''_{221}, C''_{331}, C''_{231}) \in \{(0, 0, 1), (0, 1, 0)\}$, which leads to exactly two non-isomorphic algebras, denoted by A_{29} and A_{30} . □

1.3 Derived Jordan algebras

Definition 6. A commutative algebra A is called a Jordan algebra if it satisfies

$$(x^2 y)x = x^2 (yx).$$

A commutative algebra A is called a derived Jordan algebra if the derived algebra A^2 is a Jordan algebra.

It is clear that any derived commutative associative algebra is a derived Jordan algebra. The variety of derived Jordan algebras contains all Jordan algebras. Let A be a derived Jordan algebra. If either $A^2 = A$ or $A^2 = 0$, then A is a Jordan algebra.

Theorem A3. Let \mathcal{J} be a complex 3-dimensional derived Jordan algebra. Then \mathcal{J} is a Jordan algebra listed in Proposition 3, or a derived commutative associative algebra listed in Theorem A2, or it is isomorphic to one of the following algebras:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}_{01}^\alpha &: e_1 e_1 = e_1 & e_1 e_2 = \frac{1}{2} e_2 & e_2 e_3 = e_1 & e_3 e_3 = e_1 + \alpha e_2 \\ \mathcal{J}_{02} &: e_1 e_1 = e_1 & e_1 e_2 = \frac{1}{2} e_2 & e_2 e_3 = e_1 & e_3 e_3 = e_2 \\ \mathcal{J}_{03} &: e_1 e_1 = e_1 & e_1 e_2 = \frac{1}{2} e_2 & e_2 e_3 = e_1 & \\ \mathcal{J}_{04}^\alpha &: e_1 e_1 = e_1 & e_1 e_2 = \frac{1}{2} e_2 & e_2 e_3 = e_2 & e_3 e_3 = \alpha e_1 \\ \mathcal{J}_{05} &: e_1 e_1 = e_1 & e_1 e_2 = \frac{1}{2} e_2 & e_2 e_3 = e_2 & e_3 e_3 = -4e_1 + e_2 \\ \mathcal{J}_{06} &: e_1 e_1 = e_1 & e_1 e_2 = \frac{1}{2} e_2 & e_3 e_3 = e_1 & \\ \mathcal{J}_{07} &: e_1 e_1 = e_1 & e_1 e_2 = \frac{1}{2} e_2 & e_3 e_3 = e_2 & \end{aligned}$$

All algebras, excepting $\mathcal{J}_{01}^\alpha \cong \mathcal{J}_{01}^{-\alpha}$, are non-isomorphic.

Proof. $A^2 = \mathcal{J}_{04}$. Then the nontrivial multiplications in A is given as follows:

$$A : e_1 e_1 = e_1 \quad e_1 e_3 = C_{131} e_1 + C_{132} e_2 \quad e_2 e_3 = C_{231} e_1 + C_{232} e_2$$

$$e_1e_2 = \frac{1}{2}e_2 \quad e_3e_3 = C_{331}e_1 + C_{332}e_2$$

Then with the change of basis: $e'_1 = e_1$, $e'_2 = e_2$, $e'_3 = -C_{131}e_1 - 2C_{132}e_2 + e_3$, we can make $C_{131} = C_{132} = 0$. So we assume $C_{131} = C_{132} = 0$. Hence the nontrivial multiplications in A is given as follows:

$$A : e_1e_1 = e_1 \quad e_1e_2 = \frac{1}{2}e_2 \quad e_2e_3 = C_{231}e_1 + C_{232}e_2 \quad e_3e_3 = C_{331}e_1 + C_{332}e_2$$

Whence, A is a Jordan algebra if $C_{231} = C_{232} = C_{331} = C_{332} = 0$.

- If $C_{231} \neq 0$, then with the change of basis:

$$e'_1 = e_1 + \frac{2}{3}C_{232}C_{231}^{-1}e_2, \quad e'_2 = C_{231}^{-1}e_2, \quad e'_3 = -\frac{2}{3}C_{232}e_1 - \frac{8}{9}C_{232}^2C_{231}^{-1}e_2 + e_3,$$

we can make $C_{231} = 1$ and $C_{232} = 0$. So we assume $C_{231} = 1$ and $C_{232} = 0$, therefore the nontrivial multiplications in A is given as follows:

$$A : e_1e_1 = e_1 \quad e_1e_2 = \frac{1}{2}e_2 \quad e_2e_3 = e_1 \quad e_3e_3 = C_{331}e_1 + C_{332}e_2.$$

- If $C_{331} \neq 0$, then, with the change of basis: $e'_1 = e_1$, $e'_2 = C_{331}^{\frac{1}{2}}e_2$, $e'_3 = C_{331}^{-\frac{1}{2}}e_3$, we get the family of algebras \mathcal{J}_{01}^α . Moreover, $\mathcal{J}_{01}^\alpha \cong \mathcal{J}_{01}^\beta$ if and only if $\alpha = -\beta$.
 - If $C_{331} = 0$ and $C_{332} \neq 0$, then by changing $e'_1 = e_1$, $e'_2 = C_{332}^{\frac{1}{3}}e_2$, $e'_3 = C_{332}^{-\frac{1}{3}}e_3$, we get the algebra \mathcal{J}_{02} .
 - If $C_{331} = C_{332} = 0$, we get the algebra \mathcal{J}_{03} .
- If $C_{231} = 0$, then we have the following multiplication table:

$$A : e_1e_1 = e_1 \quad e_1e_2 = \frac{1}{2}e_2 \quad e_2e_3 = C_{232}e_2 \quad e_3e_3 = C_{331}e_1 + C_{332}e_2$$

- If $C_{232} \neq 0$ and $C_{331} + 4C_{232}^2 \neq 0$, then with the change of basis:

$$e'_1 = e_1 + \frac{C_{332}}{C_{331} + 4C_{232}^2}e_2, \quad e'_2 = e_2, \quad e'_3 = -\frac{2C_{332}}{C_{331} + 4C_{232}^2}e_2 + \frac{1}{C_{232}}e_3$$

we get the family of algebras $\mathcal{J}_{04}^{\alpha \neq -4}$. Moreover, $\mathcal{J}_{04}^\alpha \cong \mathcal{J}_{04}^\beta$ if and only if $\alpha = \beta$.

- If $C_{232} \neq 0$, $C_{331} + 4C_{232}^2 = 0$ and $C_{332} = 0$, then with the change of basis:

$$e'_1 = e_1, \quad e'_2 = e_2, \quad e'_3 = C_{232}^{-1}e_3,$$

we get the algebra \mathcal{J}_{04}^{-4} .

- If $C_{232} \neq 0$, $C_{331} + 4C_{232}^2 = 0$ and $C_{332} \neq 0$, then with the change of basis:

$$e'_1 = e_1, \quad e'_2 = C_{332}C_{232}^{-2}e_2, \quad e'_3 = C_{232}^{-1}e_3,$$

we get the algebra \mathcal{J}_{05} .

- If $C_{232} = 0$ and $C_{331} \neq 0$, then with the change of basis:

$$e'_1 = e_1 + C_{332}C_{331}^{-1}e_2, \quad e'_2 = e_2, \quad e'_3 = C_{331}^{-\frac{1}{2}}e_3,$$

we get the algebra \mathcal{J}_{06} .

- If $C_{232} = 0$ and $C_{331} = 0$, then $C_{332} \neq 0$ and with the change of basis:

$$e'_1 = e_1, \quad e'_2 = e_2, \quad e'_3 = C_{332}^{-\frac{1}{2}}e_3,$$

we get the algebra \mathcal{J}_{07} .

□

1.4 Bicommutative algebras

Definition 7. An algebra is called a bicommutative algebra, if it satisfies the following identities

$$a(bc) = b(ac), \quad (ab)c = (ac)b.$$

It is easy to see if A is a bicommutative algebra, then

$$((a \circ b) \circ c) \circ d = ((a \circ b) \circ d) \circ c. \quad (1)$$

Thus, A^+ is a derived commutative associative algebra. If A is commutative, then it is associative. Let us call commutative algebras satisfying the identity (1) as bicommutative⁺ algebras.

Proposition 8. Let A be a complex 3-dimensional bicommutative⁺ algebra. Then A is a commutative associative algebra listed in Proposition 2 or isomorphic to one of the following algebras:

$$\begin{array}{lll} M_{04}^\alpha & : & e_1e_3 = e_1 \quad e_2e_3 = \alpha e_2 \\ M_{05} & : & e_1e_3 = e_1 \quad e_3e_3 = e_2 \\ M_{06} & : & e_1e_3 = e_1 + e_2 \quad e_2e_3 = e_2 \\ M_{07} & : & e_1e_3 = e_1 \quad e_2e_2 = e_1 \\ A_{01}^{0,0,\gamma} & : & e_1e_1 = e_1 \quad e_2e_2 = e_2 \quad e_3e_3 = e_1 + \gamma e_2 \\ A_{03}^\alpha & : & e_1e_1 = e_1 \quad e_2e_3 = e_2 \quad e_3e_3 = \alpha e_1 \\ A_{11} & : & e_1e_1 = e_1 \quad e_3e_3 = e_1 + e_2 \\ A_{16} & : & e_1e_1 = e_1 \quad e_1e_2 = e_2 \quad e_3e_3 = e_1 + e_2 \\ A_{17} & : & e_1e_1 = e_1 \quad e_1e_2 = e_2 \quad e_3e_3 = e_1 \\ A_{20} & : & e_1e_1 = e_1 \quad e_1e_2 = e_2 \quad e_3e_3 = e_2 \\ A_{24}^1 & : & e_1e_1 = e_2 \quad e_1e_3 = e_1 \quad e_2e_3 = e_2 \\ A_{26} & : & e_1e_1 = e_2 \quad e_1e_3 = e_1 + e_2 \quad e_2e_3 = e_2 \\ A_{27} & : & e_1e_1 = e_2 \quad e_3e_3 = e_1 \\ A_{29} & : & e_1e_1 = e_1 \quad e_2e_3 = e_1 \\ A_{30} & : & e_1e_1 = e_1 \quad e_3e_3 = e_1 \end{array}$$

1.4.1 Preliminaries: the algebraic classification

In this subsection, we introduce the techniques used to obtain our main results (the techniques are similar to those considered in [2]).

Definition 9. Let (A, \cdot) be a bicommutative⁺ algebra. Let $Z^2(A, A)$ be the set of all skew symmetric bilinear maps $\theta: A \times A \rightarrow A$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} (x \cdot y) \cdot z &+ \theta(x, y) \cdot z &+ \theta(x \cdot y, z) &+ \theta(\theta(x, y), z) &= \\ &(x \cdot z) \cdot y &+ \theta(x, z) \cdot y &+ \theta(x \cdot z, y) &+ \theta(\theta(x, z), y), \\ x \cdot (y \cdot z) &+ x \cdot \theta(y, z) &+ \theta(x, y \cdot z) &+ \theta(x, \theta(y, z)) &= \\ &y \cdot (x \cdot z) &+ y \cdot \theta(x, z) &+ \theta(y, x \cdot z) &+ \theta(y, \theta(x, z)) \end{aligned}$$

For $\theta \in Z^2(A, A)$ we define on A a product $*_\theta: A \times A \rightarrow A$ by $x *_\theta y := \theta(x, y)$.

Lemma 10. Let (A, \cdot) be a bicommutative⁺ algebra and $\theta \in Z^2(A, A)$. Then (A, \cdot_θ) is a bicommutative algebra, where $x \cdot_\theta y := x \cdot y + x *_\theta y$.

Now, let (A, \cdot) be an algebra and $\text{Aut}(A)$ be the automorphism group of A with respect to product \cdot . Then $\text{Aut}(A)$ acts on $Z^2(A, A)$ by

$$(\theta * \phi)(x, y) := \phi^{-1}(\theta(\phi(x), \phi(y))),$$

where $\phi \in \text{Aut}(A)$ and $\theta \in Z^2(A, A)$.

Lemma 11. *Let (A, \cdot) be a bicommutative⁺ algebra and $\theta, \vartheta \in Z^2(A, A)$. Then the algebras (A, \cdot_θ) and (A, \cdot_ϑ) are isomorphic if and only if there exists $\phi \in \text{Aut}(A)$ satisfying $\theta * \phi = \vartheta$.*

Hence, we have a procedure to classify the bicommutative algebras associated with a given bicommutative⁺ algebra (A, \cdot) . It consists of three steps:

Step 1. Compute $Z^2(A, A)$.

Step 2. Find the orbits of $\text{Aut}(A)$ on $Z^2(A, A)$.

Step 3. Take a representative θ for every orbit and construct an algebra (A, \cdot_θ) .

Let us introduce the following notations. Let $\{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$ be a fixed basis of an algebra (A, \cdot) . Define $\Lambda^2(A, \mathbb{C})$ to be the space of all skew-symmetric bilinear forms on A , that is,

$$\Lambda^2(A, \mathbb{C}) := \langle \Delta_{ij} | 1 \leq i < j \leq n \rangle,$$

where Δ_{ij} is the skew-symmetric bilinear form $\Delta_{ij} : A \times A \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ defined by

$$\Delta_{ij}(e_l, e_m) := \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } (i, j) = (l, m), \\ -1, & \text{if } (i, j) = (m, l), \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Now, if $\theta \in Z^2(A, A)$ then θ can be uniquely written as $\theta(x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^n B_i(x, y)e_i$, where B_1, \dots, B_n are skew-symmetric bilinear forms on A . Also, we may write $\theta = (B_1, \dots, B_n)$. Let $\phi^{-1} \in \text{Aut}(A)$ be given by the matrix (b_{ij}) . If $(\theta * \phi)(x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^n B'_i(x, y)e_i$, then

$$B'_i = \sum_{j=1}^n b_{ij} \phi^t B_j \phi, \text{ whenever } i \in \{1, \dots, n\}.$$

1.4.2 The classification Theorem

Theorem A4. *Let B be a complex 3-dimensional bicommutative algebra. Then B is a commutative associative algebra listed in Proposition 2 or isomorphic to one of the following algebras^{||}:*

\mathcal{G}_{00}	:	$e_2 e_3 = e_1$	$e_3 e_2 = -e_1$	
B_{01}	:	$e_1 e_1 = e_1$	$e_1 e_2 = e_2$	$e_2 e_1 = e_2$
		$e_1 e_3 = e_2$	$e_3 e_1 = -e_2$	
B_{02}	:	$e_1 e_1 = e_2$	$e_1 e_3 = e_2$	$e_3 e_1 = -e_2$
B_{03}	:	$e_1 e_1 = e_2$	$e_1 e_2 = e_3$	$e_2 e_1 = -e_3$
$B_{04}^{\alpha \neq 0}$:	$e_1 e_2 = (1 + \alpha)e_3$	$e_2 e_1 = (1 - \alpha)e_3$	
$B_{05}^{\alpha \neq 0}$:	$e_1 e_1 = e_2$	$e_1 e_2 = (1 + \alpha)e_3$	$e_2 e_1 = (1 - \alpha)e_3$

^{||}For receiving similar multiplication tables we have to apply the basis change $e_3 := \frac{1}{2}e_3$ in algebras B_{12} – B_{19} , B_{22} , B_{23} .

B_{06}^γ	:	$e_1e_1 = e_1$	$e_2e_2 = e_2$	$e_3e_3 = -e_1 - \gamma^2e_2$	$e_1e_3 = e_1$
		$e_3e_1 = -e_1$	$e_2e_3 = \gamma e_2$	$e_3e_2 = -\gamma e_2$	
B_{07}^γ	:	$e_1e_1 = e_1$	$e_1e_3 = \gamma e_1$	$e_3e_1 = -\gamma e_1$	
		$e_2e_3 = 2e_2$	$e_3e_3 = -\gamma^2e_1$		
B_{08}^γ	:	$e_1e_1 = e_1$	$e_1e_3 = \gamma e_1$	$e_3e_1 = -\gamma e_1$	
		$e_3e_2 = 2e_2$	$e_3e_3 = -\gamma^2e_1$		
B_{09}	:	$e_1e_1 = e_1$	$e_3e_3 = -e_1 - e_2$	$e_1e_3 = e_1$	$e_3e_1 = -e_1$
B_{10}	:	$e_1e_1 = e_1$	$e_1e_2 = e_2$	$e_2e_1 = e_2$	$e_3e_3 = -e_1 - e_2$
		$e_1e_3 = e_1 + \frac{1}{2}e_2$	$e_3e_1 = -e_1 - \frac{1}{2}e_2$	$e_2e_3 = e_2$	$e_3e_2 = -e_2$
B_{11}	:	$e_1e_1 = e_1$	$e_1e_2 = e_2$	$e_2e_1 = e_2$	$e_3e_3 = -e_1$
		$e_1e_3 = e_1$	$e_3e_1 = -e_1$	$e_2e_3 = e_2$	$e_3e_2 = -e_2$
B_{12}	:	$e_1e_1 = e_2$	$e_1e_3 = e_1$	$e_2e_3 = e_2$	
B_{13}	:	$e_1e_1 = e_2$	$e_3e_1 = e_1$	$e_3e_2 = e_2$	
B_{14}	:	$e_1e_1 = e_2$	$e_1e_3 = e_1 + e_2$	$e_2e_3 = e_2$	
B_{15}	:	$e_1e_1 = e_2$	$e_3e_1 = e_1 + e_2$	$e_3e_2 = e_2$	
B_{16}^α	:	$e_1e_3 = e_1$	$e_2e_3 = \alpha e_2$		
$B_{17}^{\alpha \neq 0}$:	$e_1e_3 = e_1$	$e_3e_2 = \alpha e_2$		
$B_{18}^{\alpha \neq \pm 1}$:	$e_3e_1 = e_1$	$e_2e_3 = \alpha e_2$		
$B_{19}^{\alpha \neq 0}$:	$e_3e_1 = e_1$	$e_3e_2 = \alpha e_2$		
B_{20}	:	$e_1e_3 = 2e_1$	$e_3e_3 = e_2$		
B_{21}	:	$e_3e_1 = 2e_1$	$e_3e_3 = e_2$		
B_{22}	:	$e_1e_3 = e_1 + e_2$	$e_2e_3 = e_2$		
B_{23}	:	$e_3e_1 = e_1 + e_2$	$e_3e_2 = e_2$		
B_{24}	:	$e_1e_1 = e_1$	$e_1e_3 = e_1$	$e_3e_1 = -e_1$	$e_3e_3 = -e_1$

All listed algebras are non-isomorphic, excepting:

$$B_{04}^\alpha \cong B_{04}^{-\alpha}, B_{06}^\alpha \cong B_{06}^{\alpha^{-1}}, B_{16}^\alpha \cong B_{16}^{\alpha^{-1}}, B_{19}^\alpha \cong B_{19}^{\alpha^{-1}}.$$

1.4.3 Proof of Theorem A4

If B^+ is trivial, then B is a metabelian Lie algebra, and we obtain the algebra \mathcal{G}_{00} . If B^+ is nontrivial, then B^+ is isomorphic to one of the algebras listed in Proposition 8. Now, assume that B^+ is one of the algebras in Proposition 8. By direct computation of the set $Z^2(B^+, B^+)$, we have the following observations:

- If B^+ is associative, then

$$Z^2(B^+, B^+) = \{0\} \quad \text{for } B^+ \in \{J_{01}, J_{03}, J_{07}, J_{08}, J_{09}, J_{10}, J_{11}\}.$$

- If B^+ is non-associative, then

$$Z^2(B^+, B^+) = \emptyset \quad \text{for } B^+ \in \{A_{20}, A_{27}, M_{07}, A_{29}\}.$$

Therefore, we focus on the following cases:

- I. $B^+ = J_{02}$. Let $0 \neq \theta = (B_1, B_2, B_3) \in Z^2(B^+, B^+)$. Then $\theta = (0, \alpha\Delta_{13}, 0)$ for some $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}^*$. The automorphism group of J_{02} consists of the automorphisms ϕ given by a matrix of the following form:

$$\phi = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & a_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & a_{33} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Let $\phi = (a_{ij}) \in \text{Aut}(\mathbf{J}_{02})$. Then $\theta * \phi = (0, \beta\Delta_{13}, 0)$, where $\beta = \alpha a_{33} a_{22}^{-1}$. Let ϕ be the following automorphism:

$$\phi = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $\theta * \phi = (0, \Delta_{13}, 0)$. So we get the algebra \mathbf{B}_{01} .

II. $\mathbf{B}^+ = \mathbf{J}_{04}$. Let $0 \neq \theta = (B_1, B_2, B_3) \in Z^2(\mathbf{B}^+, \mathbf{B}^+)$. Then $\theta \in \{\eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_3\}$, where

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_1 &= (0, \alpha_1 \Delta_{13}, 0), \\ \eta_2 &= (0, 0, \alpha_1 \Delta_{12}), \\ \eta_3 &= (0, \alpha_1 \Delta_{12} + \alpha_2 \Delta_{13}, -\frac{\alpha_1^2}{\alpha_2} \Delta_{12} - \alpha_1 \Delta_{13})_{\alpha_1 \alpha_2 \neq 0}, \end{aligned}$$

for some $\alpha_1, \alpha_2 \in \mathbb{C}$. The automorphism group of \mathbf{J}_{04} consists of the automorphisms ϕ given by a matrix of the following form:

$$\phi = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ a_{21} & a_{11}^2 & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & 0 & a_{33} \end{pmatrix}.$$

- $\theta = \eta_1$. Let ϕ be the following automorphism:

$$\phi = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha_1^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $\theta * \phi = (0, \Delta_{13}, 0)$. So we get the algebra \mathbf{B}_{02} .

- $\theta = \eta_2$. Let ϕ be the following automorphism:

$$\phi = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \alpha_1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $\theta * \phi = (0, 0, \Delta_{12})$. So we get the algebra \mathbf{B}_{03} .

- $\theta = \eta_3$. Let ϕ be the following automorphism:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \alpha_1 \\ 0 & 0 & -\alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^{-1} \end{pmatrix}$$

Then $\theta * \phi = (0, 0, \Delta_{12})$. So we get the algebra \mathbf{B}_{03} .

III. $\mathbf{B}^+ = \mathbf{J}_{05}$. Let $0 \neq \theta = (B_1, B_2, B_3) \in Z^2(\mathbf{B}^+, \mathbf{B}^+)$. Then $\theta = (0, 0, \alpha \Delta_{12})$ for some $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}^*$. The automorphism group of \mathbf{J}_{05} consists of the automorphisms ϕ given by a matrix of the following form:

$$\phi = \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon a_{11} & \varepsilon a_{12} & 0 \\ \varepsilon a_{21} & \varepsilon a_{22} & 0 \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & \varepsilon a_{11} a_{22} + \varepsilon a_{12} a_{21} \end{pmatrix} : (\varepsilon, \varepsilon) \in \{(1, 0), (0, 1)\}.$$

Let $\phi = (a_{ij}) \in \text{Aut}(\mathbf{J}_{05})$. Then $\theta * \phi = (0, 0, \beta \Delta_{12})$ where $\beta^2 = \alpha^2$. So we get the family of algebras $\mathbf{B}_{04}^{\alpha \neq 0}$. Moreover, $\mathbf{B}_{04}^\alpha \cong \mathbf{B}_{04}^\beta$ if and only if $\alpha = \pm \beta$.

IV. $\underline{B^+ = J_{06}}$. Let $0 \neq \theta = (B_1, B_2, B_3) \in Z^2(B^+, B^+)$. Then $\theta = (0, 0, \alpha\Delta_{12})$ for some $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}^*$. The automorphism group of J_{06} , $\text{Aut}(J_{06})$, consists of the automorphisms ϕ given by a matrix of the following form:

$$\phi = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ a_{21} & a_{11}^2 & 0 \\ a_{31} & 2a_{11}a_{21} & a_{11}^3 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Let $\phi = (a_{ij}) \in \text{Aut}(J_{06})$. Then $\theta * \phi = \theta$. So we get the family of algebras $B_{05}^{\alpha \neq 0}$. Moreover, $B_{05}^\alpha \cong B_{05}^\beta$ if and only if $\alpha = \beta$.

V. $\underline{B^+ = A_{01}^{0,0,\gamma}}$. Consider the change of basis $e'_1 = e_1, e'_2 = e_2, e'_3 = ie_3$. Then

$$A_{01}^{0,0,\gamma} \cong A'_\gamma : e'_1 e'_1 = e'_1, e'_2 e'_2 = e'_2, e'_3 e'_3 = -e'_1 - \gamma e'_2.$$

Hence, we may assume $B^+ = A'_\gamma$. Let $\theta = (B_1, B_2, B_3)$ be an arbitrary element of $Z^2(B^+, B^+)$. Then $\theta = (\epsilon\Delta_{13}, \alpha\Delta_{23}, 0)$ where $\epsilon^2 = 1$ and $\alpha^2 = \gamma$.

Therefore, the bicommutative algebra structures defined on A'_γ are given by the following families:

$$\begin{array}{l} X^\alpha : e'_1 e'_1 = e'_1, \quad e'_2 e'_2 = e'_2, \quad e'_3 e'_3 = -e'_1 - \alpha^2 e'_2, \quad e'_1 e'_3 = e'_1, \\ \quad e'_3 e'_1 = -e'_1, \quad e'_2 e'_3 = \alpha e'_2, \quad e'_3 e'_2 = -\alpha e'_2. \\ Y^\alpha : e'_1 e'_1 = e'_1, \quad e'_2 e'_2 = e'_2, \quad e'_3 e'_3 = -e'_1 - \alpha^2 e'_2, \quad e'_1 e'_3 = -e'_1, \\ \quad e'_3 e'_1 = e'_1, \quad e'_2 e'_3 = \alpha e'_2, \quad e'_3 e'_2 = -\alpha e'_2. \end{array}$$

Moreover, $X^\alpha \cong X^{\alpha^{-1}} \cong Y^{-\alpha}$. Hence, this case yields the family of algebras B_{06}^γ .

VI. $\underline{B^+ = A_{03}^{-\gamma}}$. Let $0 \neq \theta = (B_1, B_2, B_3) \in Z^2(B^+, B^+)$. Then $\theta = (\alpha\Delta_{13}, \epsilon\Delta_{23}, 0)$ with $\alpha^2 = \gamma$ and $\epsilon^2 = 1$. Hence, the bicommutative structures defined on $A_{03}^{-\gamma}$ are given by the following families:

$$\begin{array}{l} X^\alpha : e_1 e_1 = e_1, \quad e_1 e_3 = \alpha e_1, \quad e_3 e_1 = -\alpha e_1, \quad e_2 e_3 = 2e_2, \quad e_3 e_3 = -\alpha^2 e_1, \\ Y^\alpha : e_1 e_1 = e_1, \quad e_1 e_3 = \alpha e_1, \quad e_3 e_1 = -\alpha e_1, \quad e_3 e_2 = 2e_2, \quad e_3 e_3 = -\alpha^2 e_1. \end{array}$$

Then X^α and Y^β are not isomorphic. Moreover, $X^\alpha \cong X^\beta$ if and only if $\alpha = \beta$, and $Y^\alpha \cong Y^\beta$ if and only if $\alpha = \beta$. We obtain the families of algebras B_{07}^γ and B_{08}^γ .

VII. $\underline{B^+ = A_{11}}$. Consider the change of basis $e'_1 = e_1, e'_2 = e_2, e'_3 = ie_3$. Then

$$A_{11} \cong A'_{11} : e'_1 e'_1 = e'_1, e'_3 e'_3 = -e'_1 - e'_2.$$

So we assume $B^+ = A'_{11}$. Let $0 \neq \theta = (B_1, B_2, B_3) \in Z^2(B^+, B^+)$. Then $\theta = (\alpha\Delta_{13}, 0, 0)$ such that $\alpha^2 = 1$. The automorphism group of A'_{11} consists of the automorphisms ϕ given by a matrix of the following form:

$$\phi = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & a_{23} \\ 0 & 0 & \epsilon \end{pmatrix} : \epsilon^2 = 1.$$

Let $\phi = (a_{ij}) \in \text{Aut}(A'_{11})$. Then $\theta * \phi = (\epsilon\alpha\Delta_{13}, 0, 0)$. So we may choose ϵ such that $\epsilon\alpha = 1$ and therefore we obtain the algebra B_{09} .

VIII. $B^+ = A_{16}$. Consider the change of basis $e'_1 = e_1, e'_2 = e_2, e'_3 = ie_3$. Then

$$A_{16} \cong A'_{16} : e'_1 e'_1 = e'_1, e'_1 e'_2 = e'_2, e'_3 e'_3 = -e'_1 - e'_2.$$

So we assume $B^+ = A'_{16}$. Let $0 \neq \theta = (B_1, B_2, B_3) \in Z^2(B^+, B^+)$. Then $\theta = (\alpha\Delta_{13}, \frac{1}{2}\alpha\Delta_{13} + \alpha\Delta_{23}, 0)$ such that $\alpha^2 = 1$. The automorphism group of A'_{16} consists of the automorphisms ϕ given by a matrix of the following form:

$$\phi_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \phi_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $(\Delta_{13}, \frac{1}{2}\Delta_{13} + \Delta_{23}, 0) * \phi_2 = (-\Delta_{13}, -\frac{1}{2}\Delta_{13} - \Delta_{23}, 0)$ and we have B_{10} .

IX. $B^+ = A_{17}$. Consider the change of basis $e'_1 = e_1, e'_2 = e_2, e'_3 = ie_3$. Then

$$A_{17} \cong A'_{17} : e'_1 e'_1 = e'_1, e'_1 e'_2 = e'_2, e'_3 e'_3 = -e'_1.$$

So we assume $B^+ = A'_{17}$. Let $0 \neq \theta = (B_1, B_2, B_3) \in Z^2(B^+, B^+)$. Then $\theta = (\alpha\Delta_{13}, \alpha\Delta_{23}, 0)$ such that $\alpha^2 = 1$. The automorphism group of A'_{17} consists of the automorphisms ϕ given by a matrix of the following forms:

$$\phi_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \phi_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $(\Delta_{13}, \Delta_{23}, 0) * \phi_2 = -(\Delta_{13}, \Delta_{23}, 0)$. So we get the algebra B_{11} .

X. $B^+ = A_{24}^1$. Let $0 \neq \theta = (B_1, B_2, B_3) \in Z^2(B^+, B^+)$. Then $\theta = (\alpha\Delta_{13}, \alpha\Delta_{23}, 0)$ such that $\alpha^2 = 1$. The automorphism group of A_{24}^1 consists of the automorphisms ϕ given by a matrix of the following form:

$$\phi = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ a_{21} & a_{11}^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $\theta * \phi = \theta$ for any $\phi \in \text{Aut}(A_{24}^1)$. So we get the algebras B_{12} and B_{13} .

XI. $B^+ = A_{26}$. Let $0 \neq \theta = (B_1, B_2, B_3) \in Z^2(B^+, B^+)$. Then $\theta = (\alpha\Delta_{13}, \alpha\Delta_{13} + \alpha\Delta_{23}, 0)$ such that $\alpha^2 = 1$. The automorphism group of A_{26} consists of the automorphisms ϕ given by a matrix of the following form:

$$\phi = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ a_{21} & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $\theta * \phi = \theta$ for any $\phi \in \text{Aut}(A_{26})$. So we get the algebras B_{14} and B_{15} .

XII. $B^+ = M_{04}^{\alpha \notin \{0, \pm 1\}}$. Let $0 \neq \theta = (B_1, B_2, B_3) \in Z^2(B^+, B^+)$. Then $\theta = (\alpha_1\Delta_{13}, \alpha_2\Delta_{23}, 0)$ such that $\alpha_1^2 = 1$ and $\alpha_2^2 = \alpha^2$. The automorphism group of $M_{04}^{\alpha \notin \{0, \pm 1\}}$ consists of the automorphisms ϕ given by a matrix of the following form:

$$\phi = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & a_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $\theta * \phi = \theta$ for any $\phi \in \text{Aut}(\mathbb{M}_{04}^{\alpha \notin \{0, \pm 1\}})$. So we get the families of algebras $\mathbb{B}_{16}^{\alpha \notin \{0, \pm 1\}}$, $\mathbb{B}_{17}^{\alpha \notin \{0, \pm 1\}}$, $\mathbb{B}_{18}^{\alpha \notin \{0, \pm 1\}}$, and $\mathbb{B}_{19}^{\alpha \notin \{0, \pm 1\}}$. Moreover, $\mathbb{B}_{16}^\alpha \cong \mathbb{B}_{16}^\beta$ if and only if $\alpha = \beta$ or $\alpha = \beta^{-1}$; $\mathbb{B}_{17}^\alpha \cong \mathbb{B}_{17}^\beta$ if and only if $\alpha = \beta$; $\mathbb{B}_{18}^\alpha \cong \mathbb{B}_{18}^\beta$ if and only if $\alpha = \beta$; $\mathbb{B}_{19}^\alpha \cong \mathbb{B}_{19}^\beta$ if and only if $\alpha = \beta$ or $\alpha = \beta^{-1}$.

XIII. $\mathbb{B}^+ = \mathbb{M}_{04}^{-1}$. Let $0 \neq \theta = (B_1, B_2, B_3) \in \mathbb{Z}^2(\mathbb{B}^+, \mathbb{B}^+)$. Then $\theta = (\alpha_1 \Delta_{13}, \alpha_2 \Delta_{23}, 0)$ such that $\alpha_1^2 = 1$ and $\alpha_2^2 = 1$. The automorphism group of \mathbb{M}_{04}^{-1} consists of the automorphisms ϕ given by a matrix of the following forms:

$$\phi_1 = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & a_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \phi_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & a_{12} & 0 \\ a_{21} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $(\Delta_{13}, \Delta_{23}, 0) * \phi_2 = (-\Delta_{13}, -\Delta_{23}, 0)$ and we have \mathbb{B}_{16}^{-1} , \mathbb{B}_{17}^{-1} , and \mathbb{B}_{19}^{-1} .

XIV. $\mathbb{B}^+ = \mathbb{M}_{04}^0$. Let $0 \neq \theta = (B_1, B_2, B_3) \in \mathbb{Z}^2(\mathbb{B}^+, \mathbb{B}^+)$. Then $\theta = (\alpha \Delta_{13}, 0, 0)$ such that $\alpha^2 = 1$. The automorphism group of \mathbb{M}_{04}^0 consists of the automorphisms ϕ given by a matrix of the following form:

$$\phi = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $\theta * \phi = \theta$ for any $\phi \in \text{Aut}(\mathbb{M}_{04}^0)$. So we get the algebras \mathbb{B}_{16}^0 and \mathbb{B}_{18}^0 .

XV. $\mathbb{B}^+ = \mathbb{M}_{04}^1$. Let $0 \neq \theta = (B_1, B_2, B_3) \in \mathbb{Z}^2(\mathbb{B}^+, \mathbb{B}^+)$. Then $\theta \in \{\eta_1, \dots, \eta_5\}$ where

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_1 &= (\alpha_1 \Delta_{13} + (1 - \alpha_1^2) \alpha_2^{-1} \Delta_{23}, \alpha_2 \Delta_{13} - \alpha_1 \Delta_{23}, 0)_{\alpha_2 \neq 0}, \\ \eta_2 &= (\Delta_{13} + \alpha_1 \Delta_{23}, -\Delta_{23}, 0), \\ \eta_3 &= (-\Delta_{13} + \alpha_1 \Delta_{23}, \Delta_{23}, 0), \\ \eta_4 &= (\Delta_{13}, \Delta_{23}, 0), \\ \eta_5 &= (-\Delta_{13}, -\Delta_{23}, 0). \end{aligned}$$

The automorphism group of \mathbb{M}_{04}^1 consists of the automorphisms ϕ given by a matrix of the following form:

$$\phi = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & 0 \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Let $\eta = (\gamma_1 \Delta_{13} + \gamma_2 \Delta_{23}, \gamma_3 \Delta_{13} + \gamma_4 \Delta_{23}, 0)$ and $\phi = (a_{ij}) \in \text{Aut}(\mathbb{M}_{04}^1)$. Then

$$\eta * \phi = (\gamma'_1 \Delta_{13} + \gamma'_2 \Delta_{23}, \gamma'_3 \Delta_{13} + \gamma'_4 \Delta_{23}, 0)$$

where $M_{\eta * \phi} = \phi^{-1} M_\eta \phi$, with $M_\eta = \begin{pmatrix} \gamma_1 & \gamma_2 \\ \gamma_3 & \gamma_4 \end{pmatrix}$ and $M_{\eta * \phi} = \begin{pmatrix} \gamma'_1 & \gamma'_2 \\ \gamma'_3 & \gamma'_4 \end{pmatrix}$.

Hence we may assume M_η takes one of the following normal forms:

$$M_\eta \in \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} \alpha & 0 \\ 0 & \beta \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} \alpha & 1 \\ 0 & \alpha \end{pmatrix} \right\}.$$

So if $\eta \in \{\eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_3, \eta_4, \eta_5\}$, we have:

$$M_{\eta_1} = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 & \frac{1-\alpha_1^2}{\alpha_2} \\ \alpha_2 & -\alpha_1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad M_{\eta_2} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \alpha_1 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad M_{\eta_3} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & \alpha_1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad M_{\eta_4} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad M_{\eta_5} = -M_{\eta_4}.$$

From the above normal forms, the conditions $\text{tr}(M_{\eta_i}) = 0$ and $\det(M_{\eta_i}) = -1$ (for $i = 1, 2, 3$) select exactly the normal form $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$, and therefore the corresponding representative is precisely $(\Delta_{13}, -\Delta_{23}, 0)$. The matrix M_{η_4} corresponds to the representative $(\Delta_{13}, \Delta_{23}, 0)$, while M_{η_5} corresponds to $(-\Delta_{13}, -\Delta_{23}, 0)$. Since trace and determinant are invariants under similarity, these three representatives are not in the same orbit. Hence, we obtain the algebras B_{16}^1, B_{17}^1 , and B_{19}^1 .

XVI. $B^+ = M_{05}$. Let $0 \neq \theta = (B_1, B_2, B_3) \in Z^2(B^+, B^+)$. Then $\theta = (\alpha\Delta_{13}, 0, 0)$ such that $\alpha^2 = 1$. The automorphism group of M_{05} consists of the automorphisms ϕ given by a matrix of the following form:

$$\phi = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & a_{23} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $\theta * \phi = \theta$ for any $\phi \in \text{Aut}(M_{05})$. So we get the algebras B_{20} and B_{21} .

XVII. $B^+ = M_{06}$. Let $0 \neq \theta = (B_1, B_2, B_3) \in Z^2(B^+, B^+)$. Then $\theta = (\alpha\Delta_{13}, \alpha\Delta_{13} + \alpha\Delta_{23}, 0)$ such that $\alpha^2 = 1$. The automorphism group of M_{06} , $\text{Aut}(M_{06})$, consists of the automorphisms ϕ given by a matrix of the following form:

$$\phi = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ a_{21} & a_{11} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $\theta * \phi = \theta$ for any $\phi \in \text{Aut}(M_{06})$. So we get the algebras B_{22} and B_{23} .

XVIII. $B^+ = A_{30}$. Consider the change of basis $e'_1 = e_1, e'_2 = e_2, e'_3 = ie_3$. Then

$$A_{30} \cong A'_{30} : e'_1 e'_1 = e'_1, e'_3 e'_3 = -e'_1.$$

So we assume $B^+ = A'_{30}$. Let $0 \neq \theta = (B_1, B_2, B_3) \in Z^2(B^+, B^+)$. Then $\theta = (\alpha\Delta_{13}, 0, 0)$ such that $\alpha^2 = 1$. The automorphism group of A'_{30} consists of the automorphisms ϕ given by a matrix of the following form:

$$\phi = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ 0 & 0 & \epsilon \end{pmatrix} : \epsilon^2 = 1.$$

Let $\phi = (a_{ij}) \in \text{Aut}(A'_{30})$. Then $\theta * \phi = (\epsilon\alpha\Delta_{13}, 0, 0)$. So we may choose ϵ such that $\epsilon\alpha = 1$ and hence we obtain the algebra B_{24} .

2 The geometric classification of algebras

2.1 Preliminaries: definitions and notation

Given an n -dimensional vector space \mathbb{V} , the set $\text{Hom}(\mathbb{V} \otimes \mathbb{V}, \mathbb{V}) \cong \mathbb{V}^* \otimes \mathbb{V}^* \otimes \mathbb{V}$ is a vector space of dimension n^3 and it has the structure of the affine variety \mathbb{C}^{n^3} . Indeed, let us fix a basis e_1, \dots, e_n of \mathbb{V} . Then any $\mu \in \text{Hom}(\mathbb{V} \otimes \mathbb{V}, \mathbb{V})$ is determined by n^3 structure constants $c_{ij}^k \in \mathbb{C}$ such that $\mu(e_i \otimes e_j) = \sum_{k=1}^n c_{ij}^k e_k$. A subset of $\text{Hom}(\mathbb{V} \otimes \mathbb{V}, \mathbb{V})$ is *Zariski-closed* if it can be defined by a set of polynomial equations in the variables c_{ij}^k ($1 \leq i, j, k \leq n$).

Let T be a set of polynomial identities. The set of algebra structures on \mathbb{V} satisfying polynomial identities from T forms a Zariski-closed subset of the variety $\text{Hom}(\mathbb{V} \otimes \mathbb{V}, \mathbb{V})$. We denote this subset by $\mathbb{L}(T)$. The general linear group $\text{GL}(\mathbb{V})$ acts on $\mathbb{L}(T)$ by conjugations:

$$(g * \mu)(x \otimes y) = g\mu(g^{-1}x \otimes g^{-1}y)$$

for $x, y \in \mathbb{V}$, $\mu \in \mathbb{L}(T) \subset \text{Hom}(\mathbb{V} \otimes \mathbb{V}, \mathbb{V})$ and $g \in \text{GL}(\mathbb{V})$. Thus, $\mathbb{L}(T)$ is decomposed into $\text{GL}(\mathbb{V})$ -orbits that correspond to the isomorphism classes of algebras. Let $\mathcal{O}(\mu)$ denote the orbit of $\mu \in \mathbb{L}(T)$ under the action of $\text{GL}(\mathbb{V})$ and $\overline{\mathcal{O}(\mu)}$ denote the Zariski closure of $\mathcal{O}(\mu)$.

Let \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} be two n -dimensional algebras satisfying the identities from T , and let $\mu, \lambda \in \mathbb{L}(T)$ represent \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} , respectively. We say that \mathbf{A} *degenerates to* \mathbf{B} and write $\mathbf{A} \rightarrow \mathbf{B}$ if $\lambda \in \overline{\mathcal{O}(\mu)}$. Note that in this case we have $\overline{\mathcal{O}(\lambda)} \subset \overline{\mathcal{O}(\mu)}$. Hence, the definition of degeneration does not depend on the choice of μ and λ . If $\mathbf{A} \not\rightarrow \mathbf{B}$, then the assertion $\mathbf{A} \rightarrow \mathbf{B}$ is called a *proper degeneration*. We write $\mathbf{A} \not\rightarrow \mathbf{B}$ if $\lambda \notin \overline{\mathcal{O}(\mu)}$.

Let \mathbf{A} be represented by $\mu \in \mathbb{L}(T)$. Then \mathbf{A} is *rigid* in $\mathbb{L}(T)$ if $\mathcal{O}(\mu)$ is an open subset of $\mathbb{L}(T)$. Recall that a subset of a variety is called irreducible if it cannot be represented as a union of two non-trivial closed subsets. A maximal irreducible closed subset of a variety is called an *irreducible component*. It is well known that any affine variety can be represented as a finite union of its irreducible components in a unique way. The algebra \mathbf{A} is rigid in $\mathbb{L}(T)$ if and only if $\overline{\mathcal{O}(\mu)}$ is an irreducible component of $\mathbb{L}(T)$.

Method of the description of degenerations of algebras. In the present work we use the methods applied to Lie algebras in [31]. First of all, if $\mathbf{A} \rightarrow \mathbf{B}$ and $\mathbf{A} \not\rightarrow \mathbf{B}$, then $\mathcal{D}\text{cr}(\mathbf{A}) < \mathcal{D}\text{cr}(\mathbf{B})$, where $\mathcal{D}\text{cr}(\mathbf{A})$ is the algebra of derivations of \mathbf{A} . We compute the dimensions of algebras of derivations and check the assertion $\mathbf{A} \rightarrow \mathbf{B}$ only for such \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} that $\mathcal{D}\text{cr}(\mathbf{A}) < \mathcal{D}\text{cr}(\mathbf{B})$.

To prove degenerations, we construct families of matrices parametrized by t . Namely, let \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} be two algebras represented by the structures μ and λ from $\mathbb{L}(T)$ respectively. Let e_1, \dots, e_n be a basis of \mathbb{V} and c_{ij}^k ($1 \leq i, j, k \leq n$) be the structure constants of λ in this basis. If there exist $\alpha_i^j(t) \in \mathbb{C}$ ($1 \leq i, j \leq n$, $t \in \mathbb{C}^*$) such that $E_i^t = \sum_{j=1}^n \alpha_i^j(t) e_j$ ($1 \leq i \leq n$) form a basis of \mathbb{V} for any $t \in \mathbb{C}^*$, and the structure constants of μ in the basis E_1^t, \dots, E_n^t are such rational functions $c_{ij}^k(t) \in \mathbb{C}[t]$ that $c_{ij}^k(0) = c_{ij}^k$, then $\mathbf{A} \rightarrow \mathbf{B}$. In this case E_1^t, \dots, E_n^t is called a *parametrized basis* for $\mathbf{A} \rightarrow \mathbf{B}$. In case of $E_1^t, E_2^t, \dots, E_n^t$ is a *parametric basis* for $\mathbf{A} \rightarrow \mathbf{B}$, it will be denoted by $\mathbf{A} \xrightarrow{(E_1^t, E_2^t, \dots, E_n^t)} \mathbf{B}$. To simplify our equations, we will use the notation $A_i = \langle e_i, \dots, e_n \rangle$, $i = 1, \dots, n$ and write simply $A_p A_q \subset A_r$ instead of $c_{ij}^k = 0$ ($i \geq p$, $j \geq q$, $k < r$).

Let $\mathbf{A}(\ast) := \{\mathbf{A}(\alpha)\}_{\alpha \in I}$ be a series of algebras, and let \mathbf{B} be another algebra. Suppose that for $\alpha \in I$, $\mathbf{A}(\alpha)$ is represented by the structure $\mu(\alpha) \in \mathbb{L}(T)$ and \mathbf{B} is represented by

the structure $\lambda \in \mathbb{L}(T)$. Then we say that $\mathbf{A}(\ast) \rightarrow \mathbf{B}$ if $\lambda \in \overline{\{\mathcal{O}(\mu(\alpha))\}_{\alpha \in I}}$, and $\mathbf{A}(\ast) \not\rightarrow \mathbf{B}$ if $\lambda \notin \overline{\{\mathcal{O}(\mu(\alpha))\}_{\alpha \in I}}$.

Let $\mathbf{A}(\ast)$, \mathbf{B} , $\mu(\alpha)$ ($\alpha \in I$) and λ be as above. To prove $\mathbf{A}(\ast) \rightarrow \mathbf{B}$ it is enough to construct a family of pairs $(f(t), g(t))$ parametrized by $t \in \mathbb{C}^\ast$, where $f(t) \in I$ and $g(t) \in \text{GL}(\mathbb{V})$. Namely, let e_1, \dots, e_n be a basis of \mathbb{V} and c_{ij}^k ($1 \leq i, j, k \leq n$) be the structure constants of λ in this basis. If we construct $a_i^j : \mathbb{C}^\ast \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ ($1 \leq i, j \leq n$) and $f : \mathbb{C}^\ast \rightarrow I$ such that $E_i^t = \sum_{j=1}^n a_i^j(t) e_j$ ($1 \leq i \leq n$) form a basis of \mathbb{V} for any $t \in \mathbb{C}^\ast$, and the structure constants of $\mu(f(t))$ in the basis E_1^t, \dots, E_n^t are such rational functions $c_{ij}^k(t) \in \mathbb{C}[t]$ that $c_{ij}^k(0) = c_{ij}^k$, then $\mathbf{A}(\ast) \rightarrow \mathbf{B}$. In this case E_1^t, \dots, E_n^t and $f(t)$ are called a parametrized basis and a parametrized index for $\mathbf{A}(\ast) \rightarrow \mathbf{B}$, respectively.

We now explain how to prove $\mathbf{A}(\ast) \not\rightarrow \mathbf{B}$. Note that if $\mathfrak{D} \text{er } \mathbf{A}(\alpha) > \mathfrak{D} \text{er } \mathbf{B}$ for all $\alpha \in I$ then $\mathbf{A}(\ast) \not\rightarrow \mathbf{B}$. One can also use the following Lemma, whose proof is the same as the proof of [31, Lemma 1.5].

Lemma 12. *Let \mathfrak{B} be a Borel subgroup of $\text{GL}(\mathbb{V})$ and $R \subset \mathbb{L}(T)$ be a \mathfrak{B} -stable closed subset. If $\mathbf{A}(\ast) \rightarrow \mathbf{B}$ and for any $\alpha \in I$ the algebra $\mathbf{A}(\alpha)$ can be represented by a structure $\mu(\alpha) \in R$, then there is $\lambda \in R$ representing \mathbf{B} .*

2.2 The geometric classification of algebras

2.2.1 Metabelian commutative algebras

Theorem G1. *The variety of complex 3-dimensional metabelian commutative algebras has dimension 8 and it has 2 irreducible components defined by*

$$\mathcal{C}_1 = \overline{\mathcal{O}(\mathbf{M}_{07})} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{C}_2 = \overline{\mathcal{O}(\mathbf{M}_{04}^\alpha)}.$$

In particular, there is only 1 rigid algebra in this variety.

Proof. After carefully checking the dimensions of orbit closures of the more important for us algebras, we have

$$\dim \mathcal{O}(\mathbf{M}_{04}^\alpha) = 8, \quad \dim \mathcal{O}(\mathbf{M}_{07}) = 7.$$

All necessary degenerations are given below

\mathbf{M}_{02}	$\xrightarrow{(e_1 + \frac{1}{2}e_2, e_3, te_2)}$	\mathbf{M}_{01}
\mathbf{M}_{03}	$\xrightarrow{(te_1, e_2, te_3)}$	\mathbf{M}_{02}
\mathbf{M}_{04}^α	$\xrightarrow{(e_1 + \frac{1}{2i\alpha}e_2 + te_3, 2te_1 + e_2, 2t^2(1-\alpha)e_1)}$	\mathbf{M}_{03}
$\mathbf{M}_{04}^{\frac{t}{2}}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1, te_1 + e_2, \frac{1}{t}e_2 + e_3)}$	\mathbf{M}_{05}
\mathbf{M}_{04}^{1+t}	$\xrightarrow{(e_1 + \frac{1}{t}e_2, e_2, e_3)}$	\mathbf{M}_{06}

$$\mathbf{M}_{04}^\alpha \not\rightarrow \mathbf{M}_{07} \text{ due to } \mathcal{R} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} A_2^2 = 0 \\ \text{new basis for } \mathbf{M}_{04}^\alpha : \mathcal{B} = \{f_1 = e_3, f_2 = e_2, f_3 = e_1\} \end{array} \right\}. \quad \square$$

2.2.2 Derived commutative associative algebras

Theorem G2. *The variety of complex 3-dimensional derived commutative associative algebras has dimension 12 and it has 2 irreducible components defined by*

$$\mathcal{C}_1 = \overline{\mathcal{O}(\mathbf{J}_{07})} \text{ and } \mathcal{C}_2 = \overline{\mathcal{O}(\mathbf{A}_{01}^{\alpha,\beta,\gamma})}.$$

In particular, there is only 1 rigid algebra in this variety.

Proof. After carefully checking the dimensions of orbit closures of the more important for us algebras, we have

$$\dim \mathcal{O}(\mathbf{A}_{01}^{\alpha,\beta,\gamma}) = 12, \quad \dim \mathcal{O}(\mathbf{J}_{07}) = 9.$$

It is clear that no degeneration occurs from $\mathbf{A}_{01}^{\alpha,\beta,\gamma}$ to \mathbf{J}_{07} because the dimension of the derived algebras cannot increase during degeneration. All necessary degenerations are given below.

$\mathbf{A}_{01}^{0, (1-\alpha)i\Theta, a^2\Theta^{-2}}$ $\Gamma := \sqrt{1-2\alpha+2\alpha^2}$	$\xrightarrow{(te_1, te_1+te_2, e_1+\alpha e_2+i\Theta e_3)}$	\mathbf{M}_{04}^α
$\mathbf{A}_{01}^{0, \frac{4i}{3}, 0}$	$\xrightarrow{(t^2e_1, 2te_1+\frac{3t}{2}e_2, e_1+ie_3)}$	\mathbf{M}_{07}
$\mathbf{A}_{01}^{t^{-1}, \alpha t^{-1}, 0}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1, e_2, te_3)}$	\mathbf{A}_{02}^α
$\mathbf{A}_{05}^{0, \alpha}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1, \frac{1}{t}e_2, e_3)}$	\mathbf{A}_{03}^α
$\mathbf{A}_{05}^{t, \alpha}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1, (t^{-1}-\alpha)e_2+te_3, e_3)}$	\mathbf{A}_{04}^α
$\mathbf{A}_{01}^{\alpha_{05}, \beta_{05}, \gamma_{05}}$ $\alpha_{05} = \frac{t(t^2+t-1)-\alpha(1-t^2)^2}{t\sqrt{2(1-\alpha)t-1}}, \beta_{05} = \frac{t(\alpha t^2+t-1)}{\sqrt{2(1-\alpha)t-1}}, \gamma_{05} = \frac{2\alpha^2(t-3t^3+2t^5)+2\alpha(1-t-2t^2+2t^3+3t^4-2t^6)+t(2-4t-2t^2+4t^3+\beta(2t^2-1)^3)}{t+2(\alpha-1)t^2}$	$\xrightarrow{(t^2e_1+(1-t^2)e_2, te_1+te_2, \frac{t-1-\alpha t+t^2+\alpha t^3}{2t^2-1}e_1+\frac{t(\alpha-1+t-\alpha t^2)}{2t^2-1}e_2+\frac{\sqrt{2t-1-2\alpha t}}{2t^2-1}e_3)}$	$\mathbf{A}_{05}^{\alpha,\beta}$
$\mathbf{A}_{01}^{t, t^{-3}, \alpha}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1, t^2e_2, te_3)}$	\mathbf{A}_{06}^α
$\mathbf{A}_{01}^{1, \beta, \gamma}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1, te_2, te_3)}$	\mathbf{A}_{07}
$\mathbf{A}_{01}^{\gamma t, \beta, \gamma}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1, t^2\gamma e_2, te_3)}$	\mathbf{A}_{08}
$\mathbf{A}_{01}^{t, 0, \alpha t}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1, te_2, e_3)}$	\mathbf{A}_{09}^α
$\mathbf{A}_{01}^{0, t^{-3}\gamma^{-1}, \gamma}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1, t^2\gamma e_2, te_3)}$	\mathbf{A}_{10}
$\mathbf{A}_{01}^{0, \beta, t}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1, te_2, e_3)}$	\mathbf{A}_{11}
$\mathbf{A}_{01}^{\alpha_{12}, \beta_{12}, \gamma_{12}}$ $\alpha_{12} = \frac{(\alpha+t)(1-t^3)}{(1+t^3)\Theta}, \beta_{12} = \frac{(\alpha-t)(1+t^3)}{(t^3-1)\Theta}, \gamma_{12} = \frac{(t^3-1)(\alpha^2(t^3-3)-2\alpha(t-3t^4)-t^2(3+4t-t^3-4t^7-4\beta(1-t^6)))}{(t^3+1)(\alpha^2(t^3+3)-2\alpha(t+3t^4)+t^2(3-4t+t^3+4t^7-4\beta(1-t^6)))}$ $\Theta = \sqrt{\frac{\alpha^2(3+t^3)-2\alpha(t+3t^4)+t^2(3-4t+t^3+4t^7+4\beta(t^6-1))}{t^3-1}}$	$\xrightarrow{(\frac{\alpha+t}{2t}e_1+\frac{t-\alpha}{2t}e_2+\frac{\Theta}{2t}e_3, t(t^3-1)e_2+tt^4e_1, (1+t^3)e_1)}$	$\mathbf{A}_{12}^{\alpha,\beta}$
$\mathbf{A}_{12}^{t, \alpha}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1, t^{-1}e_2, e_3)}$	\mathbf{A}_{13}^α

$A_{12}^{0, \alpha}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1, t^{-1}e_2, e_3)}$	A_{14}^α
$A_{12}^{\alpha^{-\frac{1}{2}}t^{-\frac{3}{2}}, \alpha^{-1}t^{-1}}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1, te_2, \alpha^{\frac{1}{2}}t^{\frac{1}{2}}e_3)}$	A_{15}^α
$A_{12}^{\alpha, t^{-2}}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1, t^2e_2, te_3)}$	A_{16}
$A_{12}^{\alpha, t^{-2}}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1, e_2, te_3)}$	A_{17}
$A_{12}^{t^{-3}, 0}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1, t^2e_2, te_3)}$	A_{18}
$A_{12}^{\alpha, \beta}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1, (\alpha t)^{-1}e_2, te_3)}$	A_{19}
$A_{12}^{0, \beta}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1, t^2e_2, te_3)}$	A_{20}
$A_{01}^{(t-1)\Theta^{-1}, (t+1)\Theta^{-1}, (1+2t-3t^2+4\alpha t^4)\Theta^{-2}}$ $\Theta := \sqrt{1-2t-3t^2+4\alpha t^4}$	$\xrightarrow{(te_1-te_2, t^2e_1+t^2e_2, \frac{t+1}{2t}e_1+\frac{t-1}{2t}e_2+\frac{\Theta}{2t}e_3)}$	A_{21}^α
A_{21}^0	$\xrightarrow{(t^{-1}e_1, t^{-2}e_2, te_3)}$	A_{22}
$A_{21}^{t^{-4}}$	$\xrightarrow{(t^{-1}e_1, t^{-2}e_2, te_3)}$	A_{23}
$A_{01}^{(\alpha-1)\Theta^{-1}, (\alpha-1)\Theta^{-1}, 1}$ $\Theta := \sqrt{1-2\alpha-3\alpha^2}$	$\xrightarrow{(te_1-te_2, t^2e_1+t^2e_2, \frac{\alpha+1}{2}e_1+\frac{\alpha+1}{2}e_2+\frac{\Theta}{2}e_3)}$	A_{24}^α
$A_{05}^{t^2, t^2}$	$\xrightarrow{(te_1+t^{-1}e_2, -e_2, e_3)}$	A_{25}
$A_{05}^{-\frac{t+1}{4}, 0}$	$\xrightarrow{(te_1-\frac{2t}{t+1}e_2, \frac{2t^2}{t+1}e_2, 2e_3)}$	A_{26}
$A_{12}^{-\beta, \beta}$	$\xrightarrow{(\beta t^2e_1+t^2e_2, \beta t^4e_2, te_3)}$	A_{27}
$A_{12}^{t, -t}$	$\xrightarrow{(-te_1+e_2+te_3, -te_2, e_3)}$	A_{28}
$A_{01}^{0, t^{-2}, \gamma}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1, te_2, te_3)}$	A_{29}
$A_{01}^{0, \beta, 0}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1, te_2, e_3)}$	A_{30}

□

2.2.3 Derived Jordan algebras

Theorem G3. *The variety of complex 3-dimensional derived Jordan algebras has dimension 12 and it has 7 irreducible components defined by*

$$\mathcal{C}_1 = \overline{\mathcal{O}(\mathbf{J}_{07})}, \quad \mathcal{C}_2 = \overline{\mathcal{O}(\mathbf{J}_{12})}, \quad \mathcal{C}_3 = \overline{\mathcal{O}(\mathbf{J}_{14})}, \quad \mathcal{C}_4 = \overline{\mathcal{O}(\mathbf{J}_{16})}, \quad \mathcal{C}_5 = \overline{\mathcal{O}(\mathbf{J}_{19})},$$

$$\mathcal{C}_6 = \overline{\mathcal{O}(\mathcal{J}_{01}^\alpha)}, \quad \text{and } \mathcal{C}_7 = \mathcal{O}(A_{01}^{\alpha, \beta, \gamma}).$$

In particular, there are only 5 rigid algebras in this variety.

Proof. After carefully checking the dimensions of orbit closures of the more important for us algebras, we have

$$\dim \mathcal{O}(A_{01}^{\alpha, \beta, \gamma}) = 12,$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\dim \mathcal{O}(\mathcal{J}_{01}^\alpha) &= 10, \\
\dim \mathcal{O}(\mathbf{J}_{07}) &= 9, \\
\dim \mathcal{O}(\mathbf{J}_{12}) &= 8, \\
\dim \mathcal{O}(\mathbf{J}_{16}) = \dim \mathcal{O}(\mathbf{J}_{19}) &= 7, \\
\dim \mathcal{O}(\mathbf{J}_{14}) &= 3.
\end{aligned}$$

Note that the derived algebras for $A_{01}^{\alpha,\beta,\gamma}$ and \mathcal{J}_{01}^α are isomorphic to $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_{01}$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_{04}$, respectively. But $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_{01}$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_{04}$ are in different irreducible components in the variety of 2-dimensional Jordan algebras. Since $\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_{01} \not\sim \tilde{\mathcal{J}}_{04}$, we get $A_{01}^{\alpha,\beta,\gamma} \not\sim \mathcal{J}_{01}^\alpha$. Other non-degenerations can be obtained similarly to derived commutative associative algebras due to the dimension of the square of algebras:

$$\mathcal{J}_{01}^\alpha \not\sim \{\mathbf{J}_{07}, \mathbf{J}_{12}, \mathbf{J}_{14}, \mathbf{J}_{16}, \mathbf{J}_{19}\}.$$

All necessary degenerations are given below

$\mathcal{J}_{01}^{(2i\sqrt{2t^3})^{-1}}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1, \frac{i}{\sqrt{2t}}e_2, \frac{it}{\sqrt{2t}}e_2 - i\sqrt{2t}e_3)}$	\mathcal{J}_{02}
$\mathcal{J}_{01}^{t^{-2}}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1, te_1 + t^{-1}e_2, te_3)}$	\mathcal{J}_{03}
$\mathcal{J}_{01}^{\frac{2(4+9\alpha)}{\sqrt{(9\alpha-12)^3}}}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1 + \frac{2}{\sqrt{9\alpha-12}}e_2, te_1, \frac{2}{3}e_1 - \frac{4}{3\sqrt{9\alpha-12}}e_2 - \frac{\sqrt{9\alpha-12}}{3}e_3)}$	\mathcal{J}_{04}^α
$\mathcal{J}_{01}^{\frac{-64}{\sqrt{(9t-48)^3}}}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1 + \frac{2}{\sqrt{9t-48}}e_2, te_1, \frac{2}{3}e_1 - \frac{4}{3\sqrt{9t-48}}e_2 - \frac{\sqrt{9t-48}}{3}e_3)}$	\mathcal{J}_{05}
$\mathcal{J}_{01}^{t^2}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1, te_1 + (t^3+t)e_2, \sqrt{t^2+1}e_3)}$	\mathcal{J}_{06}
$\mathcal{J}_{01}^{t^{-2}}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_1, e_2, te_3)}$	\mathcal{J}_{07}

□

2.2.4 Bicommutative algebras

Theorem G4. *The variety of complex 3-dimensional bicommutative algebras has dimension 10 and it has 4 irreducible components defined by*

$$\mathcal{C}_1 = \overline{\mathcal{O}(\mathbf{J}_{07})}, \quad \mathcal{C}_2 = \overline{\mathcal{O}(\mathbf{B}_{06}^\gamma)}, \quad \mathcal{C}_3 = \overline{\mathcal{O}(\mathbf{B}_{07}^\gamma)}, \quad \text{and } \mathcal{C}_4 = \overline{\mathcal{O}(\mathbf{B}_{08}^\gamma)}.$$

In particular, there is only 1 rigid algebra in this variety.

Proof. After carefully checking the dimensions of orbit closures of the more important for us algebras, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\dim \mathcal{O}(\mathbf{B}_{06}^\gamma) &= 10, \\
\dim \mathcal{O}(\mathbf{J}_{07}) = \dim \mathcal{O}(\mathbf{B}_{07}^\gamma) = \dim \mathcal{O}(\mathbf{B}_{08}^\gamma) &= 9.
\end{aligned}$$

The algebras \mathbf{B}_{07}^γ and \mathbf{B}_{08}^γ are non-isomorphic, but opposite up to isomorphism; while \mathbf{B}_{06}^γ is isomorphic to its opposite. All algebras obtained as degenerations from self-opposite algebras are also self-opposite, hence there are no degenerations from \mathbf{B}_{06}^γ to \mathbf{B}_{07}^γ and \mathbf{B}_{08}^γ . Thanks to [37], \mathbf{J}_{07} is rigid in the variety of associative commutative algebras, and each commutative associative algebra is in the irreducible component defined by \mathbf{J}_{07} . Thus, it is obvious that $\mathbf{B}_{06}^\gamma \not\sim \{\mathbf{J}_{07}, \mathbf{B}_{07}^\gamma, \mathbf{B}_{08}^\gamma\}$.

All necessary degenerations are given below

$B_{05}^{2t^{-1}-1}$	$\xrightarrow{(-2e_3, e_2, te_1)}$	\mathcal{G}_{00}
B_{06}^2	$\xrightarrow{(e_1+e_2, te_2, te_3)}$	B_{01}
B_{06}^2	$\xrightarrow{((t-t^2)e_1+te_2, t^3e_2+t^3e_3, t^2e_3)}$	B_{02}
$B_{05}^{2t^{-1}-1}$	$\xrightarrow{(te_1, t^2e_2, 2t^2e_3)}$	B_{03}
B_{05}^α	$\xrightarrow{(te_1, e_2, te_3)}$	B_{04}^α
$B_{07}^{-2\alpha^{-1}-1}$	$\xrightarrow{\left(\frac{2t+2t\alpha+t\alpha^2}{2(1+\alpha)}e_1+(1+\alpha)e_2+\frac{t\alpha^2}{2(1+\alpha)}e_3, t^2e_1+t\alpha^2e_2, t^3e_1\right)}$	B_{05}^α
B_{06}^t	$\xrightarrow{(e_1, t^2e_2, e_3)}$	B_{09}
B_{06}^{1+t}	$\xrightarrow{\left(e_1+\frac{(1+t)^2}{1+2t}e_2, \frac{2t(1+t)^2}{1+2t}e_2+te_3, e_3\right)}$	B_{10}
$B_{06}^{(1+t^2)^{-1}}$	$\xrightarrow{((1+t^2)^2e_1+e_2+t^2(1+t^2)e_3, -t(1+t^2)^{-1}e_2+te_3, (1+t^2)e_3)}$	B_{11}
B_{14}	$\xrightarrow{(t^{-1}e_1, t^{-2}e_2, e_3)}$	B_{12}
B_{15}	$\xrightarrow{(t^{-1}e_1, t^{-2}e_2, e_3)}$	B_{13}
B_{07}^{1+t}	$\xrightarrow{(te_1+e_2, t^2e_1, \frac{1+t}{2}e_1+\frac{1}{2}e_3)}$	B_{14}
B_{08}^{-1-t}	$\xrightarrow{(te_1+e_2, t^2e_1, \frac{1+t}{2}e_1+\frac{1}{2}e_3)}$	B_{15}
B_{07}^α	$\xrightarrow{(e_2, te_1, \frac{\alpha}{2}e_1+\frac{1}{2}e_3)}$	B_{16}^α
$B_{07}^{-\alpha}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_2, te_1, \frac{\alpha}{2}e_1+\frac{1}{2}e_3)}$	B_{17}^α
B_{08}^α	$\xrightarrow{(e_2, te_1, \frac{\alpha}{2}e_1+\frac{1}{2}e_3)}$	B_{18}^α
$B_{08}^{-\alpha}$	$\xrightarrow{(e_2, te_1, \frac{\alpha}{2}e_1+\frac{1}{2}e_3)}$	B_{19}^α
B_{07}^t	$\xrightarrow{(te_2+te_3, -t^2e_1, e_3)}$	B_{20}
B_{08}^{-t}	$\xrightarrow{(te_2+te_3, -t^2e_1, e_3)}$	B_{21}
B_{14}	$\xrightarrow{(te_1, te_2, e_3)}$	B_{22}
B_{15}	$\xrightarrow{(te_1, te_2, e_3)}$	B_{23}
B_{06}^t	$\xrightarrow{((1+t)^2e_1+t^2(1+t)^2e_2+t(1+t)e_3, te_2, (1+t)e_3)}$	B_{24}

□

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